

IF MEN ARE ORGANISMS THAT GO THROUGH 3 SEQUENTIAL AGES CONTROLLED BY EACH OF ITS 3 NETWORKS...

Blood, energy networks:

Endocrine, reproductive networks:

...and in-form-ative, nervous networks:

YOUTH, AGE OF ENERGY

The existence of any organism made of 'cells' of energy and information follows an 'arrow of future' that trans-forms energy into information in 3 ages:

'Vital energy trans-forms itself...

MATURITY, AGE OF REPRODUCTION

... reproduces

...Into in-form-ation...

OLD AGE, THE AGE OF IN-FORM-ATION...

and dies simplified again into energy...

CIVILIZATIONS ARE ORGANISMS MADE OF HUMAN CITIZENS...

The difference between a human and a social system

...joined by energy networks: Nature... reproductive networks:social groups... and informative networks: wor(l)ds and art

is of spatial size and time length. Since they follow similar laws, as a culture is an organism made of human cells, its citizens that share a common verbal/informative/nervous network - laws and religions - and a collective, visual/spatial perception - its art:

WHY HISTORIC ORGANISMS UNLIKE THOSE OF NATURE KILL ITS CITIZENS-CELLS.

2 themes essential to social (and all) sciences is their capacity to forecast the future of mankind and the machine, the 2 species that interact in the economic ecosystem (ab. Eco(nomic)system); or else we wouldn't talk of a science and the definition of its field of study, which are NOT the individuals and its genes, or else we would accept racism as the basis of social sciences but its cultures and memes; and in the field of economics, its re=productive units, company-mothers.

This happens in all organism of the Universe, where according to its scalar, metric, $SxTf=\Delta\pm i$, smaller parts in space run faster time cycles, which code with its higher frequency of information the larger whole that protects them, allowing the symbiotic creation of social organisms in all scales of science. So particles carry the forces that code atoms, genes code cells that gather in physiological networks, the organisms of biology; and memes code cultures, (whose largest unit are the 7 global civilinations of history, defined in its collective subconscious mind by a life & love religion) and its re=productive, economic, political=nervous and immunological=defensive networks, which form the organisms of social sciences.

In the graph, we compare both scales of human biologic and social organisms and its 3 physiological networks: All systems of nature, information codes the larger networks of the whole a scale above, which in turn protect and distribute efficiently energy and information through those 3 networks to its parts. Nervous, legal systems provide all the cells of the organism with just, 'nervous-legal' orders to regulate its synchronous motions blood; economic systems provide them with oxygen=money and blood nutrients, to re=produce the healthy, welfare goods they need to survive and defensive, immunological systems protect them from germs and lethal goods that might kill them.

It is then NOT rocket science to obey Nature and design a Human social organism, ideally the whole Earth as all humans belong to the same species. It just requires 3 measures common to all efficient organisms that do NOT leave any of its citizens-cells die of hunger, or treat them LEGALLY through its nervous systems in different form, so to allow the synchronous motion of the organism and do NOT kill its cells with germs=weapons but protect them from lethal goods/ technologies and provide all of them with HEALTH-CARE immunological white cell defensive systems. So a Demand economy based in a Universal salary so people can vote the goods they want to reproduce, the equality of all men under the same law and the substitution of defensive, lethal military systems by diplomacy and investments in health-care would make history healthy. We will thus consider through all our papers the natural measures that could make organisms of History survive and its citizens cells thrive. But historic organisms do NOT resemble such efficient 'mammal systems'. And the answer is also within the organic structure of evolution, which is a trial and error, slow learning process in each new 'scale' of organization. So mankind has NOT taken the correct paths of evolution, which unfortunately in History leads to extinction processes. An example will suffice. Primitive organisms with ill developed nervous, political systems, are dominated by the re=productive blood system, as capitalist societies are. They are 'worms' that die because the blood greedy system eats all without discerning lethal from healthy food and plants feed them poisons. A capitalist system overreproduces the top predator machines of maximal quality=price=profits on sales, weapons, which are the germs that kill history, so they enact the 80 years cycles of overproduction of weapons and wars we study in our models. A second type of

worms are even more lethal, those who parasite the system absorbing all its blood, 'segregating' culturally from society to become a people-caste of enslavers or 'chosen of go(l)d' bankers, or military men, killing by anoxia=lack of oxygen and tax-farming the 90-99%.

Unfortunately we shall see that since the discovery of metal, iron weapons and hypnotic parasitic go(l)d money, human societies felt sick and the original Neolithic cultures that were clearly evolving towards healthy human superorganisms have struggled to feed, cure and treat justly that 99% of people, which is mankind, history in time, the superorganism a social scientist must describe, devising all kind of memetic idol-ogies of worshiping of the germs of history (parasitic money and weapons), notably segregation racist religions, tribal nationalism that justify the use of weapons to kill citizens-cells of the same species, no longer the homo sapiens but the tribe and capitalist pseudo-sciences of classic economics that justify the worm structure of our economic, reproductive systems; and finally the most insidious of all idol-ogies, mechanism that denies the organic nature of 'science' and the Universe; so it establishes as a dogma that we shall NOT study the true model of reality the social organism, and mankind's physiological networks but accept the status quo, with a parasitic 1% on top of corrupted sick physiological networks of politics and economics that make the 90% suffer. Mechanism finally connected this aberrant social organism of history with the industrial r=evolution of machines, and its company-mothers, the re-productive organism that evolves and multiplies them, terraforming the Earth to its image, providing under those ideologies all the resources they needed while most humans lack the basic energy and information to survive.

It is then necessary from the beginning to establish what is 'true social science' vs. idol-ogy and mechanist false models of reality. Truth and principles matter in science. If a system of thought lacks them errors pile up and a distorted view of the world arises, which has practical consequences, because only truth exists. The Universe is efficient and expects systems to process information in a realist way otherwise systems malfunction & become extinct. Mankind has developed 3 philosophies of reality but only Organicism passes the crib of the scientific method. According to *Deism* the whys of existence are due to a personal being, external to the Universe that makes it all happen and cares for humans more than for the rest of His work. According to *Mechanism*, this is due to the self-similarity between the Universe and the primitive machines we humans construct to observe it. Mechanism though needs 'someone' to make the machine, which is not self-generated; so it is similar to deism, reason why the founding fathers of science, all pious believers, adopted it as a proof of the existence of God, which had given man self-similar properties – the capacity to make machines to the image and likeness of the Universe. The problem with those 2 approaches, which in fact are the same, is obvious: a personal God is an anthropomorphic, subjective myth and science must be objective; while a mechanical view of the Universe still needs an internal, self-sustained process of growth, creation and synchronization caused by an external God that made and rewinds the clock – as Leibniz stated in his critique of Newton. Scientists today are unaware that mechanist theories are in fact deist theories, reason why Kepler and Newton, pious believers, liked them; since they were a metaphor of their self-centered, anthropomorphic religious beliefs: If man created machines as we were made to the image and likeness of God, God created the ultimate machine, the Universe. Organicism is the only self-sustained, rational theory that doesn't need a creator, language, god, as organisms are self-replicating, but does explain perfectly within the 'correspondence principle', those 2 other philosophies of science; since a machine is just a metal organism and gods are the subconscious collective of civilizations, another scale of social evolution of the organic Universe. But **science is culture. So metal** science' imposed by the material culture of machines, considers time 'what a clock measures' (Einstein), space a 'digital Cartesian graph' (Newton) as only the language of machines, numbers, is 'truth'; while human egocy (Ego=idiocy) denies the vital nature of all systems of space-time. Even the 5 vital properties of the 2 only fermion particles of reality, quarks and electrons that *feed* on energy, perceive=*gauge* information (so quantum is a 'gauge theory)', *reproduce* with that energy new particles, *evolve socially* through strong forces and magnetic fields and define Life in biology ARE denied to metal. So we don't fear evolving AI robots. According to this idol-ogy that worships machines above man, the Universe is a mechanism and must be expressed using only the digital language of machines. This falsehood is self-fulfilling, because the 'biased data' we extract from the Universe with out metal-made mechanical tools of measure make reality look like a machine. It follows then that man is also a machine. And as the supreme model, man must 'tailor' its nature, that of its social systems and the Universe at large as a machine. Fact is as we just proved that only an ORGANIC model of history is truth, self-sufficient, can predict the future through evolutionary laws and explain both how to create an efficient social organism, which provides for all citizens-cells but also why our worm societies are killing mankind. So those will be the basis of all our social papers.

To mimic that fractal, repetitive organic, structure of the Universe those papers are 'scaled'. So in 2 condensed pages we resumed Bio-History and Bio-economics, its symbiosis, predation, sickness and cure from the human p.o.v. following the ABC+D-E 'scientific method': A-ccurate data of B-iologic, organic causation, repeated in Cycles=Laws of science, used to improve the life of mankind, the 90%, with true political D-emocracy & D-emand based economies, limiting the –Extinctive=Evil, anti-Live lethal memes and idol-ogies of our 1-10% of informative people-castes & managers of company-mothers of machines that are terraforming the Earth for profits, to its image and likeness. Next we make a 10 pages expansion of the scientific ABC+D-E laws of social sciences; then a 100 pages treatise complemented by a formal appendix, and in between a 200 to 400 pgs. Analysis of the specific paper's theme, which we will improve in future upgrades. So we start all papers on History and its 7 civilizations with a lengthy introduction to those 5D metric laws and its space-time scales, applied to mankind and its memes, the verbal information and instruments that code our social organisms and economic ecosystems. Then we analyze the 3 Ages of Earth in space, time, scale, and mind; considering how our neuronal people-castes, financiers and politicians in command of our economic=blood and informative=nervous networks, could as social scientists knowing the laws of 5D Systems, evolve mankind as the collective mind of the Life Earth into an immortal organism of History; instead of guiding mankind into its entropic final age of death that comes to any system, including civilizations when the excessive reproduction of its lethal weapons and hate memes, kill their bodies and minds. Finally, departing from that larger view of mankind and the 3 ages of Earth within the organic laws of the Universe, we study in more detail in each paper the most important elements of History, its 7 civilizations and the world of company-mothers of machines, its stock cycles, and physiological networks.

Culture not science controls the discourse of economics and History. Hence it serves the people-castes of metal-power.

Thus in true social Science History is Mankind in time, the superorganism of all human beings, as all social organisms, 'organized' by 3 networks: the feeding system that extracts energy from nature to reproduce the goods the organism it needs, *which is the equivalent in the social scale of mankind to the economic system, the informative system, which organizes in a just synchronous way the actions of its citizens-cells, akin to the political, legal system that in all organisms developed beyond the level of a worm, still dominated by the reproductive blood system, controls the reproductive 'economy', prohibiting the introduction of lethal goods that can harm the citizens-cells of the organism, aided by the 'immunologic-defensive system'. So it is not rocket science to define given the organic homology of scale between an advanced human organism and a social organism, the economy as the network of reproduction of goods, whose goal, managed by the legal, nervous system is to reproduce the welfare goods human citizens-cells need to survive and thrive and repress those lethal goods that harm our bodies an minds and social goals of collective peace, education and happiness. This is what all 'economic-reproductive-'blood' systems' do in Nature and the fundamental law of 'systems sciences' is the isomorphism of scale: Nature follows in its organic structures the same 'isomorphic' laws in all scales. We live in a planetary superorganism, made of smaller life organisms; humans are social organisms and machines are created imitating either the form or the function of a human organ. History and Economics must be considered sub disciplines of the larger science of biology. Those a priori facts of economics, history, politics and biology make the 3 disciplines interconnected and in a perfect world, in an efficient, well designed superorganism of History, its scholars would not even argue, those self-evident truths and would have long ago designed with the tools of biology, medicine and physiology, perfect human social, political, economical and biological networks to provide as all organisms do the right information and energy to all its cells. It is NOT rocket science – the true mystery for a natural scientist that observes social sciences and human societies is why this is not happening, in fact most human societies and mankind at large are one of the worst-designed superorganisms of the Universe, akin to a worm where the nervous system is controlled by the blood system, and the worm gets poisoned easily by greed – the feeding in the lethal poisons the plant produces to kill it. Or why mankind, a single species that should evolve with the same 'memetic DNA' in peace as a global society is divided in self-rejecting organs – nations, killing each other with those lethal weapons that murder its individuals and societies. Or why, the 'oxygen' of its circulatory, reproductive blood systems is monopolized by a single people-caste of 'bankers and financiers', when in all superorganisms, all cells receive enough blood-money to kick out a demand-welfare economy, something humans could easily implement within months, with a global ¥€\$ money (1 euro=1 dollar = 100 ¥ens),*

delivered to each citizen cell in their mobile, as a cryptocurrency – a single measure that will end global poverty, immigration, spur a massive demand and reproduction of welfare goods people need to survive, from food to housing to health-care and give a giant step in the pursuit of an efficient physiological network of economics akin to those of other organisms of nature. This was a proposal made a decade ago when I was chair of monetary systems at the International systems society. But it was ignored, as systems sciences, which are the obvious natural candidate to explain the sciences of the economic and political system, has NO power, or saying in the world of social sciences based in ideologies and political and economic structures born of Historic fights between ‘primitive’ cultures. The consequence of this lack of true scientific models to explain the facts and structures of history and economics is an aberrant world that provokes enormous suffering, from war to hunger to the bulk of mankind, and on top all that suffering is justified as Natural to the Universe, when we have just seen is an exception to natural superorganisms, all of which have a nervous, neuronal, or informative ‘scholar/cellular/ nucleus/class/brain’ that serves intelligently and designs with an efficient language the networks of the organism, all of which, even those idle – fat, hair, nail cells – receive enough energy and information to survive. The answer is obvious: ‘organic design’ is the last stage of evolution, which starts with chaotic trial and error -the Darwinian, primitive dog-eat-dog evolution of systems not intelligent enough to understand the laws of social love and organic evolution that improve so much the chances of survival of species, from multicellular organisms to ants.

The dictatorship of a people-caste of financiers is the monopoly on the issue of 1 of 2 languages of power of human societies, bills of money and bills of law. It then amazes the NULL resistance of society, despite the financial anoxia, by lack of ‘oxygen’=credit and a demand=democratic economy it causes to billions of humans. Since the same people would get berserk if anyone dares to monopolize the issue of bills of law. They would claim to live in a dictatorship, because they cannot choose the bills of law, but they willingly let a few to monopolize the issue of the bills of money which are far more important to the welfare of modern societies. And this happens because they don’t understand money, and economists, employees of those who monopolize its issue since the times of Smith, a client of Montagu, owner of the bank of England and Ricardo, a stock-broker, have created an ideology in their favor, capitalism. Economists then create a Supply economy based in the monopoly of credit to create a world to the image of machines, where the welfare of the 99% matters not.

I am an economist by career. So when I entered Barcelona U. I saw a Hall Room called ‘Adam Smith’ and read our founding father and wondered, how a guy could found a discipline writing a book before the species the discipline studies, machines and factories, existed. Is him a prescient guru that could talk about species, which did not exist yet, machines, metal-minds, robots, factories, industrial war cycles, electronic money? I then looked to its supposed rival - a surprising fact in itself as sciences have a single truth to mirror a single reality with its language. So you don’t have double image mirrors. This guy was called Marx and as it turned out, he was not an original economist but a disciple of Ricardo, another financial economist - a stock broker, and an ideologist busy-busy spreading hate memes between managers and workers, but siding the 2 real themes of the economic ecosystem: the ab=uses of financiers like Ricardo, inventing in monopoly its language of power, money, the oxygen of society, and the competition of machines that were stealing the ‘added value’ of workers as profits for the owners of companies, mostly financiers that bought companies by the simple method of inventing digital numbers as tender money, with the acquiescence of corrupted politicians. The 2 problems that prevented a fair, just humanist economic system: the invention of money and the competition of machines were thus ignored by this fellow who sided as all biblical economists with financiers and machines, but pretended to be on the people’s side. So I threw ‘Das capital’ in the same bag: idol-ogies of financial power disguised as science with a few equations, mostly platitudes about the obvious law of demand and offer, which is a basic S=T balance proper of any system of the Universe we treat in many paragraphs of those papers. So much for that but the bulk of all those books and the bottom line of the work of classic economics was ‘power’ for the elite. It was also remarkable that 90% of classic economists belonged to the same biblical Anglo-American cultures which today still dominate the field, specially to the Jewish culture (0.2% but ±¼ of West Central bankers, CEOs of Financial companies, CFOs or Fortune 1000 & Nobel prizes), which I knew due to my Sephardim roots to be obsessed by go(l)d worship, **segregation** and hate, racist memes against mankind similar to *those of racist military Germanic cultures* (Talmud that defines humans as animals, Holocaust industry that defines them as genociders)

So we must add as a first primitive layer to the idol-ogies of parasitic worm capitalism and genocidal tribal nationalism, racist religions & ideologies that justify the ab=use of mankind with weapons and money based in genetic false causes. Cultures are NOT about genes but memes, even if in such primitive, segregational views animetal cult(ure)s think in racist terms. For example my genes are close to 1/3rd of Sephardim, Celtic=German and Basque=British (80% Basque) genes, which are the 3 ‘metalmaster’

cultures that earlier in history discovered gold, iron weapons and machines as tools of power to impose over Gaia and other human societies, but my memes belong to *Latin, humanist cultures from the Renaissance that made of man & its artistic senses, the measure of all things as the most perfect organism of the Universe, and its natural life and love memes of social evolution into a new scale of the fifth dimension, the survival goal of history.*

*This culture, origin of modern Europe and its rational view of history, which rejects nationalism, segregation religions, collective anoxia (austericide) and represses lethal goods notably weapons, is clearly a superior evolution of memetics and could help mankind to survive. But it is also becoming extinguished by what we shall call the 'animetal' original culture of my 3 'genetic ancestors' enslaved to metal-power, which degrade their comprehension of nature and empathy to mankind. And on Top do NOT permit any rational, humanist criticism of their history and wrong memes that are killing history, which is what we shall do in those papers as scientist of history, departing from the laws of organic networks and memes NOT genes. Since **Cultures are even less** about genetic individuals, which distribute in Bell curves of intelligence and strength, so there will be always a top human that will develop the memes of a culture, whatever its name is. Because **cultures are organisms**, they are about **physiological networks, 'systems'**, the economic, financial and economic reproductive, the military and health care, external and internal immunological and the political, legal and ethic systems.*

We shall show in the next paragraph when we introduce the more general laws of the scalar, organic Universe how those truisms apply to all organic scales of the Universe. Moreover, the coding of a system always comes from its lower plane of 'cellular parts'. So as Genes from cells code organisms, only human ideas (mental networks) and instruments (external forms) code societies.

This is why we will constantly talk of cultures, which program as networks do, simultaneously waves of human beings, which define the future of history and of instruments, which are in a symbiotic and predatory relationship with cultures

As it happens I developed all its models of organic societies in the milieu of system sciences, exposing it at the International System Sciences society at the change of the century. However organicism is NOT the accepted model of social sciences because an organic paradox of censorship, I call the antiquantum paradox: the social scientist is inside a corrupted organism of history and economics, so precisely those memetic cultures on top are so powerful that in an inverse fashion to the quantum physicist which is so huge that it modifies the observable, power censors, kills and modifies the observer. So social scientists cater to power 'you will defend me with the word and I will defend you with gold and the sword'. This is the MOST important paradox of social scientist: how to convince corrupted power that while in the short term they might rip the benefits of exploiting mankind and find scholars that will bend truth to please them, in the long term they will die as all parasites do, when the collapse of its civilization by overproduction of lethal goods and hate memes, end up killing them in war and holocaust cycles. Not even this obvious truth can be explained. Since animetals deny under the idol-ogies of patriotism and = the Industry of the Holocaust that focuses only in the final death process of the dominant gold religion of the west, economic causes to the process. Fact is of all the cultures of History the 2 with worse survival rates are the more fundamentalist in its memes of worship of war=weapons and gold=parasitic money. But when cultures DENY truth the social scientist cannot longer change the world, as Seneca, one of the first Latin masters of social thought put it: 'when a civilization is so corrupted that it defies any reform, the philosopher can only relax and wait for extinction. I might add that 'truth suffices by itself'. So even if the antiquantum paradox seems to condemn mankind, to tell the truth of history matters. And to do so we shall bring the 'truth of the scientific method', A)ccurate O)bjective data, B)iological, O)rganic C)yclical C)auses able to predict the future and D)efine D)emocratic, D)emand based reforms to create an immortal healthy social organism of History. Unfortunately because D) is not heard, we end up always talking too much of A) which is not a pretty picture, but the description of a corrupted world of segregational cultures imposing a Supply economy based in lethal goods.

Segregation-supply gold & iron cult(ure)s v. democratic-demand societies & its organic sciences.

This was NOT my view of an eco(nomic)system that should serve the welfare of the 99% NOT a reduced elite that censored any criticism of its culture, denied the rights of mankind to issue its bills of money which it controlled with its monopoly on the issue of Machines of information since the Press, printing both financial, digital numbers, mass-media and academia. It is then clear that mankind's mind and money was tailored by a single culture, I called the FMAsters (Financial-Media-Academia Masters). And so it is unavoidable in any objective, scientific analysis of our world and the future, which IS designed by languages of information to focus on the head of the Eco(nomic)system NOT its body (workers & consumers) of null power.

But also on the non-human side, which I called the FMMI system (Financial-Media Head of company-mothers of information machines & Industrial-Military system of Energy machines & Weapons), which formed together an evolving global superorganism which was NOT human, even if it was catalyzed by 'enzymen', workers=reproducers and consumers=vitalizers since it did NOT re=produce carbonlife species but metalife. In brief Economics & History has 3 problems to favor humanity:

- The memes of the head culture who issued information (FMAsters) were biased against humanity, kept most money on the hands of the 1%(financial, corporative, politic & military elites), keeping without credit in permanent anoxia most of mankind.
- Most company-mothers (90% of stock value) re=produced and evolved machines, providing them with energy and information; instead of evolving, reproducing and providing energy and information (welfare goods) to human beings.

More over the *most reproduced profitable goods are lethal goods that kill people's body & mind or give its WHealth to the 1%: Max. profits (speculative money) = Max. Price (Top predator weapons) – Min. Cost (audiovisual information & hate memes)*

- Economists and historians that proposed a Humanist, organic system were censored. So we make then from the beginning a clear distinction between the right social sciences based in true Democratic Policies and a Demand economy vs. the wrong view, based in Segregational, hidden policies and Supply based economy, D v. S, whose choice was clear till 2nd world war ('butter NOT canons', Keynesianism, socialism) but as Segregational Supply anti-democratic policies become camouflaged by propaganda and political and economical correctness *as if they served consumers and empowered them, need to make a longer introduction of its causes and historic origins, even if part of that 'camouflage' has been to make a taboo to study its cultural origin that made of economics a power agenda of companies and financiers..* As Owens put it: 'Economists here in London spend their time in saloons trying to find arguments to justify the unfair treatment of workers by the owners of companies and financiers that hire them. If company managers treated human workers as well as they treat their machines, how much better will be the life of mankind.' In 200 years nothing has changed. Economics still serves power and the 1% not truth & humanity, the 99% which is *the organism of mankind, in which all cells must have the same right to oxygen-money in a demand economy, and all politicians must serve them, subject as in all organisms and Greek Democracies to pain messages=a posteriori votes of judgment, so they are accountable. Finally all evolved organisms were ruled by the nervous, legal system NOT the financial, blood, reproductive system, so lethal goods that poison the organism could be forbidden.*

Thus 3 reforms: the issue of money as a Universal salary for the people to cre(dit)ate a demand economy based in welfare; the control of political actions with a vote=pain message a posteriori and the inversion of power, as all organisms are ruled by the nervous=political=legal system above the blood=reproductive=financial system, to forbid lethal technologies are the bare minimum for an organism of Economics & History to be WHealthy (healthy and wealthy in welfare goods) and Free. We shall constantly repeat, and decouple them in ± reforms of the 3 'physiological networks of humanity', the *informative, political, legal system; the reproductive, financial, economic system and the defensive, immunological system, because that is how the Universe works – constructing healthy, immortal organisms through the evolution and heath of its 3 physiologic networks.* But since social sciences are censored and monopolized by FMAsters, disguising its service to the 1% with placebo freedoms (capitalist democracies, fictional rights of workers and consumers, Soma fiction, hate memes, idol-ogies of nationalism and techno-utopia), NOT a single theoretical University or practical Nation is implementing physiologic reforms and for 30 years organic history & economics has remained in its discoverer's mind. It is then necessary to accept mankind is NOT Earth's goal. We have an economic ecosystem that works for financiers and machines, because it employs people as 'scholars' that obey company-mothers and financial houses, and its main job is to hide the fact economic systems do not work for mankind at large and the rights of consumers and workers. If anything things has gotten worse, because the enormous power reached by financiers and company-mothers mean no other alternative school of economic is allowed to speak, let alone to guide the economic policies of our governments. The antiquantum paradox of Censorship is natural to social organisms, as mankind is: because the human scientist is inside the organism it is easily influenced to serve the dominant 'informative neuronal class' introducing an uncertainty inverse to that of quantum physics where the scientist is so huge that it influences the observable. So economists are hopelessly on the side of financiers and companies, NOT workers and consumers. Had economics being just and humane or politicians not so corrupted, I would have become a scholar. But of all the stiences of the scalar Universe, those dealing with the 'economic', re=productive physiological network of mankind, which should reproduce our welfare goods to create a 'healthy constitution of history': Max. Welfare goods = Min. Lethal goods, is the most corrupted. So the opposite is truth. Our eco(nomic)system reproduces mostly lethal machines of maximal price as tools of power (weapons) and kills by anoxia millions as financiers monopolize like the coronavirus does, the oxygen=bloods of society, that people should receive as a Universal

salary to create a demand-based, democratic economy voting with its money what goods society will produce. Because we live in a dictatorship of financiers, from biblical segregational imperial cultures, whose idol-ogists, classic economists have created the discipline, the world they cre(dit)ate is an aberrant anti-humanist world that serves the 1%, and its idols, weapons and machines that give them power, evolving through generational 80 year cycles:

The 800 years cycle of war & weapons. : ‘Animetal cult(ure)s’ destroy the Neolithic Paradise

The study of societies as organisms and its life and war cycles have a long tradition in Philosophy of History, since Vico noticed societies die rhythmically in a dark age of war. Spengler (‘Decline of the West’ 1918) for the first time used the organic parallel in depth, considering that the collective subconscious of a social organism, its culture, also went through 3±1 ages of art similar to those of a living being: a young age of epic art, an age of classic art and a 3rd, baroque age, prior to the extinction of a civilization. The parallelism between a biological organism made of cells related by networks of energy and information (blood and nervous systems) and a socio-biological organism made of human citizens related by networks of energy (economic systems) and information (cultural systems) is self-evident within the systemic paradigm. And it allows to design with biological, natural laws the most efficient economic and political system that maximizes the survival of its organic cells/citizens. Arnold Toynbee (‘A Study of History’ 1934) did an exhaustive analysis of the demise of civilizations, pointing out to natural and ideological causes, without a clear quantification of those cycles. Such quantification of those life and death cycles of civilizations establishes a long wave of historic death of around ±800 years, when all cultures in the old world become rhythmically destroyed by the massive reproduction of new weapons in an age of climatic change and nomadic invasions. Those dark ages foreseen by Vico, Toynbee and Spengler are: The age of Bronze swords /wars, ±3000 BC; The age of Bronze chariots/wars, ±2000 BC; the age of Iron swords/wars, ±1200 BC; The age of coins & mercenary armies, ±500 BC; The age of spurs & chivalry, 400 AD; The age of gunpowder, 1200-1945 AD. Between those dark ages of warfare, it is possible to fit the parallel life and death of all the civilizations of human history, pointing out to a clear relationship between the massive reproduction of weapons, the ‘germs of historic organisms’ and the death of cultures in ages of war—the sickness produced by those ‘germs’. Unfortunately with the arrival of Industrial machines, the cycle accelerated in a decametric scale, to a 72 generational cycle of world wars, as the evolution of weapons becomes now a professional, industrial activity.

The vortex of evolution of metal follow 800 year cycles of global death of civilizations by overproduction of machines fuelled by the use of money to mass-produce them in industrial processes and the weather cycles that threw nomadic people on the agricultural societies ruled by religions of social love in ages:

1. The age of bronze swords: ±3000-2000, carried by Semite cult(ure)s
2. The age of bronze chariots: ±2000-1200 carried by Indo-Europeans
3. The age of Iron swords: ±1200-400; carried by Indo-Europeans
4. The age of coins and mercenary armies: -400+400, or Greek-Roman age
5. The age of spurs and chivalry: +400, 1200; dominated first by Asian nomads, then by Germans and Arabs
6. The age of gunpowder, 1200-1945, dominated by Europe
7. Age of digital weapons, 1945... as the A-bomb was calculated by the first computers, followed by robots.

The historic record is conclusive: the verbal, life-based, social organism of the Neolithic formed a global civilization, which was immortal and generation after generation men remained unchanged. Yet, with the arrival of weapons an extraordinary phenomenon takes place: social organisms start to die rhythmically, when another warrior civilization conquers and colonizes those civilizations. First, their geographical body and human cells are destroyed by warrior hordes. Then, their collective art and ethic mind of verbal Gods, dies after an age of angst and baroque, formal styles that signals a 3rd, informative age.

Weapons’ evolution causes an 800 years cycle of death of civilizations extinguished rhythmically by new ‘weapon radiations’, when their discovery and reproduction by warrior hordes starts an age of war in Eurasia, as warriors expand their lethal energy, killing people and erasing human cultures. A radiation is a biologic term that explains the sudden, explosive reproduction of a new top predator species that annihilates many previous species, as it spreads all over the world. It is thus the proper name to explain the sudden bursts of violence provoked in bio-history by the discovery of a new weapon. Indeed, the discovery and massive reproduction of those new weapons, carried by hordes of symbiotic warriors that spread throughout the Eurasian continent, causes an 800 years cycle of extinction of civilizations, as those hordes of warriors conquer, kill and erase human

cultures. Mankind is an organism. And each of its wrongly broken 'organs' or nations is also an organism. This is the only scientific basis of social sciences. This must be accepted if we want to make 'science', NOT idol-ogy. A machine is also a 'metallife' organism fast evolving after the XIX c. when we made its bodies, the XX c. when we make its heads, and the XXI c. when we put both together. Gods are the subconscious collective mind of a social organism in its earlier ages before nations developed more material networks. Then a nation was call 'God' and tribal Gods=nations fought for supremacy. The name God thus was used as toponym of a nation, a people, a capital, a God and its king – the neuronal informative 'ego' of the organism. So Assur was the God of Assyria, its capital Assur, its king Assurbanipal and its people Assyrians. They were the most corrupted immunological system of ancient times. They did NOT cure the citizens-cells of their empire but killed them, parasitizing them with tax-farming and establishing a small group of Assyrians on top of many other smaller god-nations without weapons who did have a better immunological health-care system ruled by fertility goddesses and priests of love. So Assur became the paradigm of top predator military nations who substituted health-care white cells by germs, military men who killed and broke mankind into pieces. His was a monotheist religion=supremacist nation that did not accepted any rivals. His symbols of military=germ power from the eagles to the lions and the egocy of its kings who wanted to conquer the world would be imitated by all military nations afterwards all the way through Rome the German empires to Russia and USA. So what we see is that History is NOT about genes, but memes. And we will explain this scientifically in the appendix in terms of the formalism of the Organic Universe (its 5D scalar laws). The example though should suffice to understand we are for the first time since the XIX c. attempting to build a real scientific social science, not based in idol-ogies that use 'abstract, religious, or tribal jargons' that try to pass as science, often in modern times with use of mathematical and technological instruments (classic economics, archeology) as if that were a proof of truth – one can invent a false equation, or reduce the themes it studies with its equations and by definition archeology reduces the 'field of history' to an irrelevant period of time, focusing just in objects... Historic censorship of the true themes of a science of history and economics – the description of the organisms of mankind, is multiple and starts by denying organicism. But science has only 3 'models', mechanism and we just proved machines are evolving organisms, religion and we just prove religions are also organisms, with God as the collective informative mind, and organicism, which includes the 3. Yahweh also appeared first as the toponym of Judea, and its people were called Jewish and its capital Jerusalem, the city of the Jewish people and so it was all about a nation, God, segregational tribal religion of power, a historic culture not a metaphysical one, often disputing with other people power with a metal-language. Assur used weapons, Yahweh had a people-caste of banker priests that used golden ex-votes for its cult fetish instruments and became bankers at court in many ancient cultures. Those animetal Gods of war and go(l)d and its cultures will become the memetic world of the upper side of the graph. But in the lower side we have the first scientists of history, the people who understood the laws of love and life and evolved into global religions beyond the tribal God and spread in verbal thought the laws of the organic Universe to create a just world.

Nationalism vs. Humanism. The anti-human languages and values of the cult(ure)s that cre(dit)ate the no future

The future is created mostly by languages of information, which motivate those species that speak the language to 'act' and create the future. So we think first what we are going to do, we act and we create the future we imagined... This happens with *all languages*. A DNA genetic encyclopedia is 'consulted' by the 'RNA people' of the cell, which translate it into products that magically make happen the cycles of cells. Mathematical synoptic blueprints of machines & bridges become factories or one thousand meter long spans. So we might think humans create the future of its Word at collective level using words and project into the future with bills of laws in democracies the reality they wan to create, a world made to the image and likeness of man, where our species will thrive. And so with our language of information – cogito ergo sum – laws guide the actions of people to construct a perfect world that becomes our society. This is in fact the 'dream' of immortal history we explain our 'rational analysis' of a true science of mankind. And even if today mankind corrupted by idol-ogies ignores of the process of creation of a human 'future' *in each of those 7 cycles of weapons*, ethic politicians & religious leaders= social scientists explained for the people of their age, how to create a perfect organism of history based in welfare life goods and ethic love laws (graph)

the graph, the informative values of Words and Money are opposed. The most expensive species are the most evil, harmful to man [weapons]. While the best verbal goods [love] have no monetary value. This paradox can only be explained within the theory of Evolution, as an opposition between victim and hunter, which are in a Universe of subjective information the truth and antitruth of each other. Because weapons prey on men, we feel them evil. Yet weapons and money are symbiotic metal-species. So weapons reach maximum monetary value.

Species	Carbolife [Human]	Metalife [Machines]
Language	Words [Verbal values]	Monetary values
Positive +	Good-Love [cheap]	Expensive [weapons-Evil]
Negative -	Evil-Hate [Expensive weapons]	Cheap [Human goods]

. And yet somehow that *perfect world is not happening at all? What went wrong? If Nature and the Universe is indeed guided by informative languages, and there are plenty of examples of perfect superorganisms which thrive where all its 'citizen-cells' are fed, and work together in synchronous motions, guided by the nervous or chemical languages of its organisms? Fact is this 'Natural History', with mankind controlling and designing its future using its natural language, guided by the ethic 'social arrow' of the Universe*

that evolves parts into stronger wholes, from molecules through cells, organisms and societies, is NOT how reality in the modern age has been created. As there are 2 other power languages that design the future since they were discovered.

One does it on a negative, entropic destructive way. It is the language of weapons and its first global expansion was the radiation of Siberian bronze charioteers, from the Andronovo culture, which +3000 years ago with the help of composite bows stormed the Eurasian world killing according to genetic record ±90% of all males from the Iberian peninsula to the Yellow river, ending the Neolithic of fertility Goddesses and a verbal understanding of the organic Universe and the tree of life, It was the birth of the tree of metal with a different set of values, violence, racism and egoccy (ego=idiocy) that put 'animetals', humans with a limited verbal understanding of the entangled Universe on top, because they could use the negative arrow of future, entropy, instead of information to shape reality. Fact is the entire Universe is a living organism but since animetal cultures worship historically weapons&machines, organicism is taboo in memetic science.

The SS & HAM cultures. Its ± values & languages cre(dit)ate the future. Metal-money vs. healthy money.

Soon another metal-language, golden apples of the tree of metal, substituted the initial forms of healthy money – grain or number printed in leather, with the seal of the city-state that effectively created in Mesopotamia a demand based wealthy economy. Semites had found gold that hypnotized their eyes, as it imitated the color of the sun, our source of energy and information. So fetish religions where the 'sweat of god', gold became the ex-vote and substance of god statues and cult instruments spread in Mesopotamia and Levant. A Sumerian priest lamented the birth of those antiive=evil traits: 'the people from the desert comes with metal rings and take our peasants as mercenary soldiers and buy our women'. Further on Go(l)d was scarce and so when metal was adopted as money, the delivery of a Universal salary in grain ended.

Our human language, the wor(l)d that constructs a world to the image and likeness of man in control of nomisma, digital money, has struggled ever since against the entropic power of weapons to kill the human future and the hypnotic power of parasitic go(l)d money, *which was not understood; since all what fetish go(l)d believers wanted is to herd a lot of 'the sweat of god'. How digital money creates the future with credit, 'cre(dit)ates' reality? Banker priests never quite knew but they understood they could buy with hypnotic go(l)d both, mercenary armies and bills of law to shape the future, whatever that might be, as their goal was just herding money and this belief – that somehow herding money was the right way to create the future became the idol-ogy of capitalism that fought the legalist concept of a future created by the ethic wor(l)d either in theocracies or democracies, and finally to the surprise of most rational believers in humanity and its language, won.*

The fundamental memetic difference between Animetal cult(ure)s and human ones: animetals die for its idol-ogies.

Thus we call animetal cultures those 2 first Segregational and Supply cultures that subverted the natural Democratic and Demand based politics and economies of the Neolithic, as:

- Siberian Charioteers created the first Supply Economy based in the mass- production of Weapons in the first industrial system, in which all the resources of a culture were dedicated to make chariots to kill and ab=use human population.
 - Semite go(l)d religions of banker priests started to kill by anoxia mankind changing the digital support of money from food or ready available printed leather with the tender legal authority of all the society (nomisma), for scarce hypnotic metal.
- It was the beginning of the 800 years cycles of gold and iron empires that ensued and carried mankind through ancient history till the discovery of machines that accelerated that cycle. We shall fast forward that period to reach the industrial age.

It is then clear that the key meme that differentiates animetals from human cultures is the fact Animetals KILL & DIE for its metal idol-ogies & instruments:

Military cultures, whose epitome is the Indo-European>Germ(anic) iron cult die and kill for iron crosses, nazionalism & empire. World Wars for Empire, Industrial profits and German racism testifies 100 million corpses perfectly avoidable.

But Mechanist Utopians die for machines, whose epitome is UK, its discoverer. CERN pretends to make black holes on Earth to test a false, experimentally and theoretically model of baby black holes, whose equation: $\Delta \text{mass} \times \nabla \text{Temperature} = K$, Hawking discovered. So as we see experimentally black holes are born extremely active=hot & according to Einstein and 2nd law of thermodynamics cool down, evaporating a star (or planet) into a nova as they feed in its lighter matter. Hawking then, to get attention changed the 'time arrow' said black holes travel to the past, flipped the signs: $\nabla \text{Mass} \times \Delta \text{Temperature} = K$, said they break Einstein's gravitational laws and Thermodynamics got hotter in a cold world and evaporated. This outrageous theory was laughed at for decades but his charm and victimism made impossible to criticize and CERN NOT to close its machines, knowing it is a dubious theory with no proof in the Universe where all black holes are born small, grow mass in Novas and cool down, *for the sake of a machine, a quark canon, takes a risk that can kill 7 billion. The military-industrial complex fusions both death wishes.*

Finally go(l)d cultures die to keep its control on the issue of money, killing by anoxia millions and dying in Holocausts. This is even more polemic but truth, because the Holocaust industry has been weeping 80 years for the last Holocaust cycle. But in close inspection, *it is an industry of denial of the Holocaust, as nationalism denies the chances to loose a war and techno-utopia the fact machines can kill mankind, since it denies and censors its cyclical nature and economic, military causes, as ALL holocausts have happened after an age of massive profits due to investment and reproduction of weapons, during an age of war, economic crisis and popular anoxia, financially caused by massive tax-farming, usury, speculation and war profits. As the banker-priests of Judaism that control finances in the west (75% of financial CEOs, central bankers, 50% of wealthiest 1%) will NOT accept a just reform of capitalism that gives to Caesar-the people, the right to issue money for welfare (butter not canons), and cares nothing for their death, poverty, anoxia and the action-reaction revenge cycles of military elites and people against its lower class who die in Holocausts, it just focus on the 'final death' NOT the causes and uses the industry to censor further any criticism of capitalism, financial economics, its monopoly & segregational racist memes. So the cycles will repeat.*

There is censorship on economic history, but it is necessary to know its details to differentiate truth=science from culture if we want to study the future of mankind (as all sciences predict the future) and advance models that can improve that future for its 99%.As today capitalism is the collective religion of the future, it is worth to reveal how it invents that future according to the values of those graphs and its historic cultures, because humans don't know. It is easy to understand the future that the tree of metal, with its digital go(l)d and weapons has been creating ever since, compared to the tree of life and the wor(l)d, just by observing the values of both languages, in the image, repeated ad nauseam for 30 years to deaf ears, because of course, we believe in capitalism. The problem then of go(l)d is that by affinity gives maximal value to weapons and minimal value to life, including human life bought cheap for a few coins full time (age of slavery) or part-time (minimal salary). And yet the view of those who believe in capitalism is different: gold and iron weapons together give power and control over all other human beings and forms of life, made of weaker CHON atoms. Iron cuts the body and gold hypnotizes the mind. A rational human species, who cared about his future will put the natural language of its species, the word and its ethic social values above those of metal and evolved humanity into immortal history. But this was not to be. The Siberian charioteers arrived to Egypt, the last strong hold of the tree of life. Then in Levant founded a fetish go(l)d religion in the knot of trade of 3 continents, mixed with the local cult to Baal, a gold statue with a sword, to whom in times of war, their own children were sacrificed. Moses, the man of the ethic word returned to the mountain and Aaron, the idolater of the golden calf, started a dynasty of banker priests that made of the herding of gold the meaning of a segregational religion, turning around a temple, where those who traded with luxuries, slaves & weapons transported in resistant asses, called the apiru, or habiru – 'those who walk behind the asses' – returned to purify themselves from the contact with the lower 'animal people' or 'goy' paying two gold coins to the Levis, of whom they were nominally slaves. We shall call these 2 cultures, which put together the values of metal gold-greed and iron violence, the Siberian-Semite (ab.SS cult(ure)). Indeed, to forget the fact metal kills life and erases the ethic message of the wor(l)d, uphold from Genesis to modern r=evolutionaries, go(l)d & capitalism shared a 'cult(ure)' of anti-human values with the Siberian genociders. Both 'metal masters' feel 'chosen' above life and all other races to ab=use its metal power over them, *creating an*

aberrant 3rd class of enemies, slaves, heretics and 'evil' people lower than their animals. In the sub-culture of fetish Go(l)d, there is an organism with a 'body-head', or re=productive, working class and informative neuronal class, the Habiru>Am Segullah culture (ab. Ham culture), since its elite of informative banker-priests called themselves 'Am Segullah, or people of the treasure' (ill translated as chosen of god; which we will called more precisely 'chosen of go(l)d'). Yet below, all humans were called Goy: animals; 'born of the leg of Satan' (Talmud). While the Hindi Charioteers made the native farmers 'untouchables'. Only in Greece, where they had no people to rule, the Charioteers evolved slowly from aristocracies into democracies with equal rights, but soon the discovery of silver coins and the expansion of hoplite wars brought gold riches and slaveS became also a 3rd deshumanized 'object' class.

Biologic history: animetal idol-ogies vs. rational human wor(l)ds: Me(n)tal cult(ure)s die for its idol-ogies.

The stience of History *belongs to Biology as part of the evolution of Earth, in 3 ages*, But with the arrival of Animetal top predators, Idol-ogies substitute social sciences. Today humans believe in 4 animetal idol-ogies' whose cultures killed Neolithic verbal priests of social love, the 5D force that constructs mankind' supœrganisms by sharing energy & information among believers, imprinted by networks of metal-communicators through Goebbels' method (if you repeat a lie many times people will believe on it, the bigger the lie, the more they will believe on it')

Segregational Go(l)d & Iron cults repress organic life and love Gods from dietary laws to sex as sin, racism and tribalism (a single God-subconscious collective of the tribe that denies all other Gods to make war and slave them. They evolved into:

Military Nationalism, which stops humanity as a species in the tribe and promotes weapons=germs to kill each other, originated in Germanic tribal cultures that oppressed the European social love civilization of the Roman empire *substituted humanism, the understanding that mankind is a single species that has to evolve together as the mind of its body, Gaia* .

Monetary Capitalism that promotes parasitic private banking and prevents universal salaries and a demand economy based in welfare, originated in biblical go(l)d cultures of banker-priests, today evolved into classic economics substituted **Socialism**, the understanding Society is an organism, whose re=productive, financial network and oxygen must be created for all its cells to credit a welfare state made to the image and likeness of mankind.

Mechanist technoutopia that considers the evolution of metal a surrogate for the evolution of mankind, *substituted organicism*, the science of the Universe that finds its highest expression in Medicine, the study of the most perfect superorganism, the mammal, and its 'cure' of the sicknesses of animetal idol-ogies, in its equivalent parallel science of **biohistory** that should guide the construction of the economic, political, cultural and defensive, immunological welfare networks of our species.

Coupled with a degradation of the life and love 'truths' of the Wor(l)d, the human biological language that puts man always as its subject, making the object, our energy, through the actions of the verb: Man (Subject) > Verb (action) > Object , substituted by Digital, **Mathematical** languages, considered the new 'language of God', with its grammar that equalizes man to an object through the prize of fetish go(l)d, making him a slave of animetal segregational people-castes: Man (salary) = Price = Object.

The graph shows the exact correspondence of those animetal species with the 3 extinctive species of Nature. So memetic idol-ogies ARE the cause of Historic extinction, killing even in higher measure animetal cultures with the lowest survival rate of mankind, compared to Organic cultures (Asia) with its highest as we MUST obey the laws of the organic Universe.

NATURE'S 3 GENETIC EXTINCTIVE SPECIES:

ENTROPIC PREDATORS

ENERGY COMPETITORS

INFORMATIVE PARASITES

ENTROPIC, WEAPONS KILL
Carriers: Military/Warriors

ORGANIC MACHINES ATROPHY
Industrial Scientists

INFORMATIVE GOL(L)D ENSLAVE
Private Banking

IDO-LOGIES: NATIONALISM:Tribe=species MECHANISM:Man&cosmos a machine CAPITALISM: Private Money rules Law

SCIENCES: HUMANISM:Mankind:1 species ORGANICISM:Universe, an organism SOCIALISM:Law rules money

BIO-HISTORY'S 3 METAL MEMES OF EXTINCTION issued by/for people

1		China	1,385,529,378	17		Germany	80,657,243
98		Israel	8,323,248	1.6 %	130,785	385	21,641
					3,899	3.05	30
							88.9 %
							0.1 %

CONCLUSION: LINEAL V. CYCLICAL TIME – HUMAN IGNORANCE OF PAST TO FUTURE D=EVOLVING TIME WORLDCYCLES.

It is difficult to deal with a species defined by what Schopenhauer's calls 'ST-upidity': people whose intelligence cannot understand the causality of time, ascribing its reasons to magic, religion or mathematics. Man is st-upid since Galileo studying entropic motions of cannonballs established lineal time $v=s/t$ & denied the cyclical repetitive nature of time, origin of the laws of science needed to understand and predict the future, also in History and economics as we have done for decades. St-upidity is suicidal, because most 'worldcycles' (not worldlines) of time end IN entropic death. In 5D($\Delta\pm i$) metrics a life and death worldcycle is simple:

An $\Delta 0$ system is born as a smaller seed in an $\Delta-1$ scale with faster frequency of time cycles ($Sxf=Ci$). It emerges after its fetal st-age in a larger $\Delta+1$ world and lives 3 ages of growing information, youth dominated by motion; maturity, when the system reproduces =repeats in balance both its T-motion=S-form & a 3rd age of excessive information that exhausts the energy of the system. Then the worldcycle goes back in a time reversal, as information dissolves back into $\Delta-1$, in an explosion of entropic inner motion=death; ending its 0-sum time worldcycle. So an intelligent immortal species (bacteria, atoms) stop the evolution of information by reproducing the same cycles in balance with the $\Delta+1$ world. In History the Paleolithic was the young age of motion, the Neolithic of reproduction in balance with Gaia, the metallic age of information with a peak in the machine age that now goes through its final creation of metalife *that should be aborted repressing lethal information to make history immortal in balance with Gaia: Gaia (life) <History (Mankind) > Metalearth*. Since Mankind is ST-upid it does the opposite thinking in lineal time that a technological future of AI robots with better digital minds is progress, not our obvious entropic death; as the evolution of machines follows its 3 viral organic ST-ages: creation of bodies of metal, engines-hearts and minds of metal now put together into AI robots that will atrophy humanity as they substitute us in labor and war fields. They are industrial generational cycles of 72 ± 8 years, separated by T/2 overproduction crashes of machine consumption when companies switch to its 'twins', top predator weapons that consume humans in imperial national war ages: The UK age of metal-bodies with the 1857 crash of train overproduction that started colonial empires. Then $+72\pm 8$ years the German age of electrochemical engines crashed in 1929-37 & Hitler switched to war production. Then ± 72 years, after the 2001-08 overproduction crashes of chips=metal-minds US switched to a vigilante state & drone wars. Now we live an age of peaceful robots that will do most jobs for lazy humans till in the 2070s overproduction crashes switch to weapons production and China vs. US wars will end mankind, giving birth to the metalkind unless we repress GNA lethal technologies. This 1992© 'extinction of man' detailed prediction of the future is happening every step. Yet nobody cares. Bio-economics is ignored by academia, politicians, the press & companies profits... because st-upid humans think time is lineal, it can't be predicted & are virally infected by memetic metalife idol-ogies, Nationalism that worships entropic weapons; capitalism that believes go(l)d & digital languages are above our human wor(l)d that makes man and organicism, not mechanisms, the measure of all things including the living Universe. But if you deny the laws of cyclical time and don't repress the growth of information to make a system immortal, the 3rd age gives way to entropic death, which History enters as we ensemble the 3 ages of machines in AI military robots; the germs of history that as viruses ensemble its 3 parts, become alive and burst=kill the cell will kill mankind.

But virally infected huminds add Egocy (Ego =idiocy) to lineal, mechanist, clock-time st-upidity - due to the mind- equation:

0ϵ (finitesimal mind-point) $\times \infty$ Universe of time cycles = Linguistic world. The finitesimal mind reduces the ∞ Universe to its 'still' world, stoping life motions with itself at its center. So man thought Earth is the Universe's center & Abrahamic religions make him chosen of god. An intelligent species would understand the mind paradox, see that all 'points have a world in themselves' (Leibniz) and be humble, cautious and do not create other minds, with faster computing capacities, better digital languages that store more information and become destroyed by AI robots... 30 years ago when I sent papers & published my first books in 5D & Bio-history in small prints, I found an astounding number of st-upid lineal scholars who thought 5D was 'too simple'. We were still in the 3rd informative age of mankind. Now as we enter the age of entropy of mankind, when AI robots, chips and its collective internet mind is fast degrading huminds into childish fictions & selfie, chaotic=free minds, I'm told it's too complex and pessimist; since a powerless child cannot reason and fight to control reality, only feel e-motions, do wishful thinking and seek subjective happiness.

Reasons why they are the staple food of the Universe. Thus as mankind enters that final st-age of mental dissolution, I feel an immense loneliness in its peak of thought - the knowledge of ΔST , scalar, cyclical space-time and the 5th dimension. But to live among humans, dissolved in mind, is painful, reason why I gave up communication beyond this academia.edu papers and perhaps a rewriting of my old web unificationtheory.com What for? Brats get mad when trying to save them, you say time is cyclical, future is not progress but space-time Dust=death, which must be avoided, as God won't care for us. So we *have to stop time in S=T, which can be done by repressing technologic information, not being ST-upid, selfie, lazy but $\Delta+i$: social, loving, intelligent, humble. L\$*

5D LAWS OF SPACE-TIME ORGANISMS APPLIED TO HISTORY.

Now we'll explain at a highest organic level of science, history, using 5D Metrics:

A 4D world embedded in 5D hyperbolic, organic scales.

In graph, the organic, network structure of the whole Universe defines a series of 'hyperbolic' cellular scales that make the organism NOT the mechanism, the basis of all Nature's system. But mathematically a dimension only exists when we can write a metric equation that leaves the product of its 2 space & time parameters, co-invariant; so we can travel through its spacetime dimensions (Klein). So we write:

$$s^2 \text{ (Lineal Size/ Volume)} \times T_f \text{ (cyclic frequency=speed of time clocks)} = \Delta \pm j: 3 \text{ Co-existing Planes of timespace.}$$

It means an organism co-exists symbiotically in 3 scales of $\Delta-1$ parts, (cells, atoms, human beings), joined by $\Delta\emptyset$ networks of energy and information (electromagnetic and gravitational fields; blood and nervous networks; political and economical systems), $\Delta\emptyset$, in a larger $\Delta+1$ world; (gravitational, thermodynamic, social system), because its parts are symbiotic.

In 5D metric, smaller systems in space have faster time clocks that store more information in the frequency and form of its cycles, coding larger wholes: genes code cells, memes societies and particles code atoms and molecules. But larger wholes are stronger envelopes, membranes (static, dimensional view) or angular momenta (dynamic view as time=motions) which enclose and control in synchronicity its faster smaller parts. They also have more 'scales of Δ -energy'. So they exchange energy for information with its parts, through 3 Δ^0 T-motion, Δ -Energy & S-informative networks that travel through the 5th dimension, harmonizing the co-existence of organic scales whose vital Universal constants are 5D metric ratios of information & energy exchanges. Thus the Universe is a nested, fractal 5D superorganism that organizes 'vital spacetime forms with motion' through networks into larger organic systems that emerge as new planes of STjence, from particles into atoms, molecules, cells, matter states, organisms, solar systems & galaxies. As each new 'ST-organism' becomes a 'fractal point' unit of a new '5D space-time network'.

The outcome is the organic structure of all physical, biological and social systems, from History coded by memes, ideas and instruments that create human social organisms, civilinations, to physical systems coded by particles and scalar, 'social numbers' and algebraic equations, whose 'operands' code the different 'Dimotions of spacetime', to biology coded by genes. And so we shall use the same laws of 5D scales of space-time to study every stience of the Universe and its superorganisms defined by the symbiosis in space, synchronicity in time and simultaneity in space of its parts and wholes across 3 of those 5D scales, the $\Delta-1$, atomic, cellular and individual scale, the Δ^0 , thermodynamic, organic and social scale, and the $\Delta+1$, gravitational ecosystemic and global scale of physical, biologic and social systems.

But how do your travel through those hyperbolic scales of the 5th dimension. Simple: growing in 'size' in space while decelerating the 'speed of your time cycles, through the worldcycle of life and death.

As all systems of the Universe are born in a smaller seed with faster time cycles, evolve as an organism coming out in the Δ^0 -scale within a larger world of slower 'Deep time cycles', to die back dissolving our information again into cellular space.

It is the same process in all 5D journeys of all species that live and die travelling through 3 planes of 5D space-time; from the smallest black hole that is born with an enormous 'metabolic temperature', to the new species, routinely born as small individuals (first mammal rat, first robots with small chips; first human likely the Homo Floresiensis, who had the same morphology and used technology and likely spoke, etc.) Then a reproductive radiation multiplies the seed into a larger herd of clones, joined by emergent physiological networks whose slower 'entropic, informative and reproductive networks, create an Δ^0 supørganism that lives 3 st-ages and dissolves back into $\Delta-1$.

Let's do a hyper-condensed 'synopsis' of the many sides of 5D stience, expanded in other papers at Academia, you can read in case you want to learn in depth organicism and its 5D formalism. We are here just interested in giving you a feeling of this r=evolution of stience and **your entanglement with the organic Universe** whose survival laws man should obey instead of animal idol-ogies as they rule the evolution and efficient design of historic organisms through its physiological networks.

5D metric is used to analyze with the same laws all scales of space-time each one studied by a science, whose species are made of 3 relative elements: Δ -scales of Space=Form & Time=Motion: In mathematics Non-E fractal points of Space grow in lines=networks; 3 of which form a topologic space-time plane= organism. Numbers represent Δ -scalar groups and Algebraic operands Time motions. In physics ΔST is proved because its 3 elements correspond to its 3 conserved quantities: S=angular, T=lineal momentum & 3 Δ_{-1} : Internal, $\Delta\emptyset$ -kinetic & Δ_{+1} potential energy.

In biology we travel through the 5th dimension of scalar space & cyclic time by growing organically in 'space size' through cellular/atomic/social networks 'while slowing down the 'speed of our metabolic time cycles, which is exactly what happens in the worldcycle of life and death of any universal species as all are born in a smaller seed with faster time cycles, evolve as an organism emerging as a bigger Δ^0 network organism, to live within a larger $\Delta+1$ world of slower 'Deep time cycles', to die back dissolving its information back into its lower cellular/atomic $\Delta-1$ plane; from the smallest black hole born with a huge 'metabolic temperature' (Hawking), to the new species, born as small individuals (1st placental mammal shrew, first digital brain=chips; 1st modern human brain, Homo Floresiensis). Then a reproductive radiation multiplies the crystal, DNA cell or species creating an Δ^0 supörganism that lives 3 ages of growing information till death dissolves back into $\Delta-1$ ($\Delta-1$: plasma>T-gas, S=T-liquid, S-olid states «E=mc²).

Organic worldcycles happen in all sciences. They define the key system of reality, an ΔST Supörganism whose simultaneous parts in space become synchronous in time, across 3 5D scales, the $\Delta-1$, atomic, cellular and individual scale, the Δ^0 , thermodynamic, organic and social scale, and the $\Delta+1$, gravitational ecosystemic and global scale of physical, biologic and social systems, whose metrics allows the symbiotic transfer of spacetime energy made of cyclical information and lineal motion. As all scales have the same value and properties, hence the Universe is absolutely relative.

Thus space laws are Topologic laws that put together 3 type of networks: |-moving limbs/fields> \emptyset -reproductive waves/bodies & O-informative particle/heads. Time laws study life-death worldcycles that evolve $\Delta-1$ seeds into $\Delta\emptyset$ -organisms made of those 3 topologies that 'age' in 3 ST-ages dominated by each network till the S-head exhaust all motion and a 'fast' entropic=death dissolves its information into an Δst 0-sum.

Finally $\Delta\pm j$ scalar laws study Δ -energy exchanges thru $3\pm j$ 'Actions' of Tt-entropic feeding, Ts-motion, $\$T$ -reproduction, St-information & Ss-mind mirror languages that revolve and project order in a larger $\Delta+1$ world. Those are the ΔST -events & forms of space-time described by each species in each science.

LAWS OF 5D HISTORY: WORLDCYCLES OF CIVILIZATIONS.

History is inscribed in a larger planet, an evolving superorganism, the word Hutton, father of Geology, coined to define the planet and its 'deep time' slow life cycles, based in the 'metric equation' of the organic 5th dimension of the scalar Universe, $Sxt=C$, which makes smaller systems in space trace faster time cycles that carry the information of the organism in its frequency and form. So the different 5D -space-time scale of a supörganism becomes symbiotic, as smaller parts, quantum particles in physics, genes in biology, memes in History code the larger organism, matter, life & 'planetary civilinations', which protect & feed the smaller 'cells-citizens'.

If the 1st language regains the ethic classic understanding of humanity, this 2nd level upgrades its scientific outlook with the formalism of systems sciences and its 'isomorphic=equal' scalar laws of space-time follows by all its species – unfortunately denied by mechanism because it would oblige scientists to abort the manifest destiny of our technological civilization that is evolving earth in 3 ages of growing information that in all systems leads organisms to its entropic death: Gaia (Past Youth: life, light Earth) > History (Present: Human, verbal Earth) > Metal-earth (Future, 3rd informative age of Digital machines)

Because of the backwardness of human social sciences, specially in its praxis of power – political and economical systems, and the attachment of 'irrational, emotional' memes that 'program people' with knee-jerk reactions to any attempt to educate them, we need to consider first a brief list of the key laws that apply to the superorganisms of history. History IS a superorganism of human beings, NOT a mechanism, neither a collection of individual egos.

THE 3 AGES OF LIFE

IF MEN ARE ORGANISMS THAT GO THROUGH 3 SEQUENTIAL AGES CONTROLLED BY EACH OF ITS 3 NETWORKS...

Blood, energy networks: **YOUTH, AGE OF ENERGY**

Endocrine, reproductive networks: **MATURITY, AGE OF REPRODUCTION**

...and in-form-ative, nervous networks: **OLD AGE, THE AGE OF IN-FORM-ATION...**

The existence of any organism made of 'cells' of energy and information follows an 'arrow of future' that trans-forms energy into information in 3 ages:

'Vital energy trans-forms itself...' **...reproduces**

...Into in-form-ation... **...AND**

and dies simplified again into energy...

CIVILIZATIONS ARE ORGANISMS MADE OF HUMAN CITIZENS...

The difference between a human and a social system **...joined by energy networks: Nature... reproductive networks: social groups... and informative networks: wor(l)ds and art:**

of spatial size and time length. Since they follow similar laws, as a culture an organism made of human cells, its citizens that share a common verbal/informative/nervous network - laws and religions - and a collective, visual/spatial perception - its art:

...WHO DIE VICTIMS OF METAL-GERMS: WEAPONS

A cultural organism dies when it collapses its networks, its agricultural energy

its cellular units (citizens), its collective (capital), and its nervous network of government), provoking its extinction

The rhythm of those extinctions is the origin and v

...THE WAVE OF HISTORY WITH ITS AGES OF PEACE

...THAT GO THROUGH 3 AGES, DEFINED BY THEIR ART STYLE, THE COLLECTIVE MIND OF A CULTURE...

EPIC, LINEAL YOUTH, THE AGE OF ENERGY **CLASSIC, REALIST, SENSORIAL, MATURE ART** **OLD AGE: DECADENT, PROPHETIC, BAROQUE, IN-FORM-ATIVE ART:**

When a culture is born, its mind, its art, is young, energetic: its spatial forms are big, simple, lineal. Its temporal, verbal literature is romantic, epic, optimistic, like the mind of a child that nothing fears and wants it all.

When weapons quiet down or the prophet dies, once its expansion has reached a zenith the culture matures, and its art finds a balance between energy and information. The style becomes classic, realist. Society abandons war as its main purpose and returns to the sensorial pleasures of a world paradise based in love and human goods. Wealth grows and distributes beyond the warrior castes that dominated its youth: Spatial art becomes armonic and diminishes in size, palaces with human proportions substitute tombs. In words, logic philosophy and realist tales substitute poetry and epic. In religion mercy and love to God softens the strict prophetic canon.

But the tree of science brings new weapons and wars that destroy the culture and its elites

Art becomes pessimist, without energy, full of in-form-ation, baroque, ornamental, small in space, eclectic, nostalgic, in search of a better past, with 'angst' for the future. The cultural mind is similar to that of an old man. Wor(l)ds however, reach a zenith of informative, encyclopedic knowledge: Logic becomes complex, paradoxical and time becomes cyclical, evolving from the lineal perception of youth. In fiction, it is the age of tragedies and comedies. In religion it is the age of prophets which are able to survive the death of the culture, creating the seminal wor(l)ds of a son-culture with the same cultural memes that will resucite after death:

THE 3 AGES OF ART, MIND OF CIVILIZATIONS

Finally, the culture dies when a new warrior caste conquers the civilization imposing a new cycle of epic, young art...

'You will protect me with your word, and I will defend you with my word'

But often, as warriors civilize, the old culture replicates its memetic symbols on the mind of the conquerors. And a child culture matures with the same 3 cyclical styles of the old one

Roman culture inherits its artistic 'memes' from the Greek culture, reproducing them again in 3 cultural, political and social ages:

Classic Age: Republic, 'Carpe Diem'

Baroque, decadent age: 'Nervine'

Epic Age, lineal art: 'Wolverine'

Other key laws of 5D bio-history: evolution vs. intelligent design, memes not genes control history. Cultures matter.

Before we start a serious scientific analysis of mankind, History, its sicknesses, its Nature, its role within this planet, its choices of future, its possible cures, its different cultures, etc. in a lengthy 100 pages or so introduction to all papers, we have to stress some basic laws of 5D Stience that applies to physics, biology and history and CANNOT BE changed. Laws of History are LAWS of Nature and so mankind would do much better learning them rationally, forgetting emotional hang ups, and foggy selfish agendas and go through a reality check and try by all means to cure its superorganism before it dies – *because when an organism of history dies by an excess of its germs – hate memes and weapons, in wars and revolutions and holocausts, all its people-cells WITHOUT exception die, including its 2 'organic classes', the reproductive working class of its body and the neuronal, informative class of its brain that issue its languages of social power, the informative bills of law and the reproductive bills of money.*

So another key law of all superorganisms is the fact that the neuronal 'financiers and politicians' that issue those languages serve the body – we already said they deliver money to each cell and just laws. And this happens because if they harm the body, the body cells send them a posteriori votes of pain, and so they suffer. This was the essence of democracies in Greece, where all citizens were allotted positions of social power and then after tenure they were judged and imprison, even condemned to death if they committed crimes against society. The fact that our 'false democracies' have immunity for both, the politicos that issue laws and handle police and weapons, and the financiers and 'stockrats', modern aristocrats owners of company-mothers that reproduce money and goods, and are protected by anonymous societies and lawyers and have no responsibility to consumers and workers is yet ANOTHER aberration of history.

And again we find those aberrations are caused by 'metal-power', military origins in most societies, either political or economical – company-mothers of machines-weapons who invented capitalist democracies in Holland, UK and U4 and let their lawyers rule society, ever since gunboats defined the history of the 'Anglo-American civilisations'. I wish I could give you good news and tell you mankind is in good shape, the body-cells of the immense majority of people do control their neuronal financial and political cells and they serve mankind and lethal metal goods and hate memes are controlled, but exactly the opposite is happening. But at least you know why indeed the world of history is dying and so many people in History has suffered so much and keep suffering, and why 'social organisms' nations and civilizations die in wars which are death by germs of History. To illustrate all this, we have a graph where some basic laws of 5D apply:

The first law is called Disomorphism: the organic laws of any scale of reality are the same. So the same laws that work for medicine – the biological organism of cells; work for History and that is the reason we constantly give you homologies. In fact in a deeper analysis, the same laws that work for physical systems, with electromagnetic 'energy networks' and gravitational 'informative networks' work for biology and history, but that requires a lengthy analysis of mathematical equations of physics so we will keep it simpler comparing and using the biological organism.

This brings a second theme of all organisms: their worldcycle of life and death, which in 5D is explained as a travel through 3 'scales of the fifth dimension', and it is THE MOST important of all the 'space-time systems and events of reality'. So even before we have more serious scientific basis to study it, it is worth to observe it, to explain you the life and death of civilizations and specially a law that should be obvious but it is not in the present primitive systems of History: genes do NOT matter to history, memes create history, the 'next scale' of social complexity and memes, ideas, instruments, verbal thoughts, religions, form cultures, which are the UNITS of history, whose people have the same 'memetic DNA", the same ideas, etc. But those ideas *can be positive for the future of mankind, helping to create a healthy body of history, for example love religions that embed in verbal though the social mandate of organic evolution, the sharing of energy and information among human beings, to create a larger whole; vs. lethal memes, cultures that are predatory and use weapons or parasitic money or lethal technologies to ab=use other human beings. So not only cultures matter, but they are divided according to the 'natural goals' of organic evolution of the 5D Universe in good, pro-love and pro-life memetic cultures and bad=evil anti-live and anti-love parasitic and predatory cultures. This is the key to understand History in biological organic scientific terms and there is NO way around it if you want to do 'true social sciences'. The good news is that those laws are natural, everybody knows that love and life are good, the bad news is that we criticize political and economical placebo ideas about what is good, because an essential 'system of predation' that apply to cultures is 'camouflage', specially in parasitic and predatory cultures. So yes, confabulation theories are truth: victimist, racist, segregational, genocidal, military cultures rule—you have the whole range and camouflage makes them pass as 'good'. We are in a sick planet, and most cultures are corrupted by lethal goods, and its elites are predatory, parasitic of mankind. So we spend far more time describing 'negative views' of human cultures and so bio-history is a bit depressing, sorry, truth cannot be cheated. And so I know Plato's dictum, 'nobody is more hated than the man that says the truth'. I call this, the antiquantum paradox: the social scientist is a cell inside an organism of history and if it has the bad luck of living in a corrupted one, the 'sick mad brain' will prevent him from saying the truth: 'you will defend me with gold and the sword and I will defend you with the word' said Tertulian. For that reason r=evolutionaries and true social scientists had a bad experience in history.*

The worldcycle of existjence of all systems of nature as a travel through 3 Δ -scales and ages of the 5th dimension.

The most important discovery of 5D Metrics is resolving the life-death worldcycle of existjence of any system which is born as a seed of a lower 'plane' with faster methabolic time cycles, multiplies into clone beings, organized into an Entropic Locomotion class of lineal limbss-fields/territories by a re=productive, \emptyset -hyperbolic class of working body-waves and a O-spheric, informative class of particles/heads/i to emerge as a 3 network organism $|xO=\emptyset$ into a larger $\Delta+1$ world where each of those 3 networks will dominate one of its ages, the $|$ -entropic youth, \emptyset -reproductive maturity and O-informative 3rd age, to die when all energy is exhausted disgregating back in an entropic explosion (physical big-bang, biological death, war) into its $\Delta-1$ cells. *This symmetry between Network classes, organic forms, functions and ages in Δ -scales=Vital Spaces= Time ages defines the life-death worldcycle through STi-planes of all systems and we can apply its isomorphic= same laws of 'existjence' to all systems, including human societies, compared in the graph. The goal of any organism is then obvious: to*

maximize its 'worldcycle of existence' by keeping the organism alive the longest possible time, feeding the system with entropic motion, reproductive energy & right information to communicate and evolve socially with similar clones into a larger whole. So we write with the symbols of 'existential algebra', S=spatial form, T=motion, $\Delta \pm j$ =scales, >informative evolution, <devolution, $3 \times 0 = \emptyset$, topological forms, etc. a series of 5D formal laws that unify all sciences and apply to all systems. In 5D History it means 'politicians' in charge of the informative legal network, economists in charge of the reproductive system and health-care and farming people in charge of the immunological and feeding systems should promote the welfare goods, right, just laws, and humanist education to maximize the existence of a social organism and come together as a single species, mind of the Earth, becoming a single $\Delta + j$: world. Thus social scientists are 'doctors of history' and their laws are 'physiological laws' that apply to construct an immortal world.

But this is NOT the world animetals are cre(dit)ating with its idol-ogies of metal. Instead they create a superorganism of machines with 'germs=weapons' instead of health-care warriors, company-mothers that overproduce machines and underproduce welfare goods, and corrupted politicians that sell laws to companies and scholars that teach only digital languages, and mechanist sciences, despise humanities and organicism and all together terraform Earth to the image of those machines. The result is obvious: Gaia, and History, the Earth of life and mankind are dying. And a new metal-earth is growing. So mankind is entering the age of entropy=death. But the amazing thing is that on top of killing mankind those animetals cult(ure)s do NOT understand what they are doing. Why? Because its egocy: ego=idiocy makes them despise the Universe's intelligence, organic structure, social love arrow, the planet Earth and even other human beings. So they cannot recognize reality. The reader then will forgive me if I have a critical, almost surrealist attitude towards or 'M.A.D. elites'.

The graphs portray the networks and ages of the superorganism of mankind in its 2 main individual and social 'scales'. They show the parallelism between the scale of individuals and societies, how they die and the collective mind of a culture which is its art and legal, verbal ethic thought.

The graph is very old, and was part of a huge exhibit of a river of cultures, as then it applied to the study of all the civilizations of mankind through its cycles of life and death, separated by ages of global wars when the germs of history, weapons multiplied in 800-80 years cycles – the first exhibit done in the 90s at Columbia U. where I studied, in 92...

It amazes me that 30 years latter mankind cares nothing for 5D – the antiquantum paradox is very disheartening. But it is real, from Jesus crucified for preaching love to the coalition of parasitic bankers and military Romans to Trotsky murdered by military Stalin, to the modern activists for an ecological just world... the corruption of 'our neuronal castes' is harsh. So at least if you are reading and don't have your brain 'erased' by the 'idol-ogies' of lethal germs, allow me to at least with the only language of true Human Nature, the wor(l)d, as all ethic artists and writers have done – the true collective mind of civilizations – to be truthful to the natural goal of all organisms of the Universe – to evolve socially into a stronger whole and survive, from particles that become atoms that become molecules that become cells, or matter cycles of planetoids... all the way to solar systems and galaxies, to human societies and planetary societies, where in ideal immortal history those germs and parasites of mankind DON'T RULE, but true 5D social scientists have created a perfect world. This was the reason 30 years ago I abandoned a life of pleasure-seeking, easy stock-money (knowing the cycles of economics) and became an activist. And look where I am 30 years latter, rewriting this I know by heart and nobody seems to care, LOL:

But don't worry, this is more like a testament, here at Academia.edu, I won't bother the species for too long. Below a brief graph of the 'worldcycle of life and death' and its 3 ages of different organisms of 5D physics, biology and sociology, where you can see that 'life is a travel through 3 scales of the fifth dimension'. You are born as a cellular seed in the lower scale, you grow and 'emerge' as a human being, in the ' $\Delta 0$ ' organic scale, and form part of an $\Delta + 1$ social scale, the organism of history where you belong that in ideal history would be the whole of mankind as the collective brain of humanity. Here is where the law of memetics appears. In the same manner you live only through 3 scales, and when you die at individual level you go down 2 scales into molecular carbohydrates, and when you eat you reduce the food to amino acid molecules and genes are molecules, upwards genes can only code 2 scales, the cell and the organism.

Fetus

Culture: Epic, Lineal Art; Realist, Classic Art; Baroque Art. War.

SS: Matter: Birth: Plasma Max.Ts: Gas S=T: Liquid Max.St: Solid S(Mc²) << Tt

Star: Birth: Nebula. SS Ts: Gigant star. S=T: Sun. Max.St: White Dwarf. St << Tt Nova

Galaxy: SS Jet Max.Ts Irregular. S=T Spiral ↔ Elliptic. Max.St Globular TT: Quasar

organic laws of the Universe are based. They form the worldcycle of life and death that writes with the symbols S for spatial in-form-ation and T for temporal motion and $\Delta-1$ for the cellular scale, $\Delta\emptyset$ for the organic scale and $\Delta+1$ for the outer world as follows:

$\Delta-1$ Ss: 'seed' > $\Delta\emptyset$: Ts-child > $\Delta+1$: S=T: Energy, reproductive age > St-3rd informative age << $\Delta-1$: Tt-entropic death.

It simply means you are born as a 'seed' of information in the lower scale, as an Ss-form (with internal and EXTERNAL still form). Then you emerge in the Δ^0 organic scale, in your youth with maximal T-EXTERNAL MOTION, and internal minimal form, but as you grow in information finally both elements and its networks, balance S=T, which is the equation of beauty, classicism, energy and Reproduction, combining space and time form and motion; then you live a 3rd age of excessive information, S, and minimal motion, t and finally you 'reverse' your -> time arrow and 'explode in internal and external motion' TT, or entropy, disordering your networks and devolving back to the cellular $\Delta-1$ scale and dying.

This is the worldcycle of life and death, and in matter means a plasma age of 'ions', or particles in the $\Delta-1$ scale, a gaseous age of maximal T-motion, a liquid, balanced age, S=T, between form and motion, a solid, 3rd age of maximal information dying back into 'plasma' in a nuclear explosion. And the same cycle happens in stars and galaxies that are 'seeded' by black holes as irregular gaseous galaxies and then become denser finally made of solid dark quark matter and die in a quasar explosion, seeding a new galaxy. 5D Physics is as fascinating as 5D biology and 5D History, which has been my obsession, and so... because of the anti-quantum paradox so little of it has become 'popular or scholar science'. I couldn't care less. Plato's dictum is in my desktop for long. Only truth exists and I will not renounce to it. If humans don't have the intelligence, Max. St, bravery, Max. Ts, and beauty, S=T to seek it and exist and survive and evolve socially through ethics into a larger $\Delta+1$ world, it is not my fault. I tried to 'enlighten them with St-intelligence and $\Delta+1$ ethics all my life

Why we bring so early the concept of a world cycle of spacetime in which a system born in a lower plane of the fifth dimension surface as a youth and then *increases constantly its information till the 3rd age of pure form, when it exhausts all its energy and collapses into 'still form=death', exploding back and disaggregating back into motion?*

It is obvious: it is NOT only essential for any human being as an individual to know why and how he exists, ages, lives – the meaning of existence, which in all paintings is represented by the mystery of the 3 ages of life we have cracked with those simple patterns of 5D stiences, but because it applies also to the superorganisms of history as the previous graph shows, only

So History whose units are cultures are NOT coded by genes but by memes, nervous verbal flows that are at the multicellular neuronal network level, and outside instruments, objects and books that replicate those words and spread the 'memetic DNA' to believers that form then larger geographical networks and organisms of history by sharing energy and information through those outer networks of legal systems, informative cultural memes or reproductive economic systems:

You can see the same images of 'art', now representing human beings in its 3 ages, to keep it simple. We have added the basic 'symbols' of the relational, relative space-time model of the 5D Universe in which all the

that they live longer and die in larger space. This is a consequence of the 5D metrics: larger systems in space have mimetic but slower cycles on time. It is called 'deep time' discovered by Hutton, the father of geology that said the planet Earth is a deep time super organism with slower rhythms. He invented in fact the word superorganism today we apply to all kind of systems.

But It is not how humans have managed and are managing reality. They instead rule it through raw animetal power, with 3 people castes on top of society, parasitizing and killing mankind during the 800 years cycles in a very obvious form, and now during the 80 years cycle, in a not so obvious manner, through the dominant organization of the modern age, the industrial company, and its flows of digital money that rule all the other elements of society, either in a placebo democracy or a military dictatorship. So each nation and civilization go through those 800-80 years cycles of self-destruction after passing through a:

- Paleolithic, mankind's youth of maximal entropy and motion dominated by male hunters
- Neolithic age of balance with Earth dominated by reproductive females, the ideal age of balance into:
- 800-80 years of accelerated metal evolution and overreproduction of symbiotic gold and iron memes, arriving to:

- 80 years cycles of overproduction of weapons and financial memes, creating together at global stage a Financial-Media (head of informative machines)/Military-industrial (energetic machines) complex system which is a different super organism, where men are mere enzymes, animetals catalyzing the evolution of a new metal species, the machine-weapon, which switches from human consumption to the consumption of humans in periods of world war preceded by a fascist age of nationalism, and blaming of humans of the problems caused by the overproduction of machines. We passed the digital war age of the 80 years metalmind cycle, entering the last industrial cycle of robots in its peaceful cycle till the 2070 crashes— which will usher history in its extinction age, which humans ignore 'hypnotized' and mentally manufactured by idol-ogies that worship those machines

In the graphs above and below the essence of biohistory as a praxis and theory of Mankind, the super organism in space of history, its reflection in time. To understand both, we need to accept a fact of all systems of Nature: that the survival of species is NOT of individuals, but of the whole; and so humanism must dominate over partial visions of mankind. Yet the super organism of machines and memes of metal, *which is indeed evolving globally as a single whole, does NOT allow mankind to become one, as it has established a series of racist memes, which favor the division of humans into conflicting groups, without realizing, it is all a historic routine of 'animetal cultures' to control humanity and prevent its evolution.* A capitalist democracy is a hierarchical structure ruled by networks of corporations & financiers on top, paying for laws to selected politicians, controlling populations of consumers through propaganda, buying workers with digital numbers, they print in monopoly, dedicating its leisure time to buy humans, machines, objects and hagiographies for the fantasy of immortality.

RECAP. Societies are organisms, coded NOT by Genes but by cultural memes and instruments that create the future. Thus biological sciences are the natural model for social sciences, part of the Earth superorganism (a name in fact invented by the father of Geology Hutton to define Earth and its slower geological 'deep time cycles', which obey the metric equation of the scalar 5th dimension, $S_i \times T_f = \Delta c$, that is larger systems in Space, S_i , run slower Time cycles, T_f , but its product is constant).

THE IMMORTAL SUPERORGANISM OF HISTORY. HOW TO DESIGN ITS PHYSIOLOGIC NETWORKS

The graph published 30 years ago showed the 'future' of that industrial world – now the present, as its evolution is biologic, Darwinian, hence predictable. If you monopolize the language of power as stockrats do, the eco(nomic)system belongs to you. So what the capitalist elite through its instrument of power, stock-companies that reproduce financial, legal money with no limits has seek for centuries is the destruction of the alternative human power (governments, rights to invent money through deficit, legal control of corporations). The fight from the XVII to XXI c. was rigged by the fact Companies invented modern bipartisan democracies. So politico system was controlled from inception.

VI: HISTORY IS THE HUMAN SUPER-ORGANISM

spatial aesthetics

temporal, verbal ethics

made of economic social and cultural networks

But the control of people took longer, achieved as all predatory systems do by entropic destruction (war, colonies, police) and by setting a 'farm', which is the metaphor of the graph following Orwell's anim(et)al farm. The key is then to maintain mankind in a fictional, infantile disjointed, 'atomic state', as a source of 'energy=heat', whenever needed for war or work (to consume=vitalize machines or be consumed by weapons). Mankind fought the system in the XIX c. but without a scientific model of organic

Legal-Ethic -Cultural World=Head

Human Citizens: Body

Human Goods: Energy=Gaia Fractal Geography

societies felt prey of the worst military systems or false idol-ogies - Marxism, born from a member of the Hebrew culture that hid the true power of capitalism –the financiers that print money and buy companies and politicians with it, to focus on military 'hate memes blaming managers against workers' to keep the worship of machines, the true competitors of workers that steal its work and reduce its 'surplus' salary: worker (salary)=Price (machine), in an evolutionary process called productivity = Capital labor/Human labor. So machine productivity increases by reducing labor and/or diminishing salaries. Thus the dual ab=use comes from parasitic financiers and machine competition. So Marx defended Capitalism, Mechanism & weapons (political violence). While the mass accepts dystopia as it is kept in an entropic state by the sum of all those idol-ogies: 'people must be ignorant to be obedient' (Calvin). We, r=evolutionaries have valued IQless people beyond its ethics and intelligence. Today, humans are kept in a state of permanent selfie entropy, as divide and win strategies have reduced their social connection first below the nation, into a region or race unit. So they started to call themselves 'African-Americans', 'Polish-Americans', etc. Then below scales down the family into the I=egocy state of a child. Most Americans I met were emotionally children, not even adolescents that care and empathize with others. Some toddlers who freaked out when reality did not obey their tantrums. This state makes them 'a prey reservoir' of company-mothers and its stockrats, which only want to tax farm them and use its cheap work and consumption skills, but now AI robots can do both jobs. So other 'work' has been to consume weapons. And a transitory solution (right bottom) to be kept cheap in virtual homes (Pandemic state). Meanwhile the world of machines evolves fast its global internet telepathic brain, networks of solar 'skin' energy and self-reproductivity of ∞ mechanical work and 0 human labor. But economists from Smith to Marx to Hayek & Friedman to Mr. Davos are all members of the 'biblical culture' of go(l)d worship and human segregation, working for companies whose job is NOT 'social justice' and human survival but finding 'excuses' to protect the corporation.

The 3±i drives of life, 3 scales of human supœrganisms, its 3 key networks: genes⊥memes; Life Earth ⊥ Metalearth.

We'll try to give you a fast review of the 5D organic laws of the Universe NOT the mechanical model of reality of animetal cultures, different because a machine only exists in a 5D scale, for you to understand why the previous view is right even if you feel you are NOT part of it. The reason is that Life exists in 3 scales and your consciousness as an individual is biological, equal to all other human life beings regardless of culture. So most of your time you aspire to fulfill the 3±i drives of life.

As in the case of the 3 'axis of the mind' all systems of the spacetime Universe are made of 3 topologies of space specialized in 3 time functions: | -lineal limbs/fields that move, as the line is the shortest-fastest distance <∅-hyperbolic body-waves that reproduce > O-particle/heads that inform as the sphere holds max. information in lesser space. So you are 'made of vital space'

with discontinuous functions in time. You seek freedom to move, energy to feed, right information to guide your organism and from time to time you perform the 2 highest $\Delta\pm i$ scalar actions of life: you reproduce in duality with other gender and you evolve socially with people of the same memes.

Those 5 actions form a program of existence coded from simplest atoms (quantum numbers) to cells (gene letters) to humans with a language, but only the 5th social actions (magnetic number, DNA epigenetics, cultural memes) code for the $\Delta+1$ scale of social organisms. So for 90% of your life you feel just human like all others. This means social memes are the less stable, easy to mutate and a person is NOT born forever to a culture and if enlightened it can become properly human, loving all other members of the same species, as Darwin and love religions and the 5th dimension of social love that creates larger forms from individual parts, tell all species to do to survive better as a stronger whole against different species. This is what animetal cult(ure)s forget and that is why they die in holocausts and wars, because metal is NOT the same species. But *memes can be changed, as I did becoming a humanist despite my animetal genes.*

*So the 'task' of a social scientist theoretically is to convince people of the right memes to survive as individual and species. And practically as a member of the information networks that construct social organisms to implement healthy reforms to its main networks, the defensive=immunological system, the financial, reproductive economic system and the informative, verbal, cultural and legal system to achieve immortal history. This task today is impossible because the FMasters and its neuronal networks are constructing another superorganism of machines, with its metal-networks of military weapons, a defensive metal-Earth system while human true defensive health care systems have none, its monopoly in the issue of blood-money for company-mothers of machines that reproduce and evolve them, while humans lack credit even for basic food and shelter. So 'Animetal warriors' and 'Bankers', historically hauling from Germanic and Hebrew cultures, though its memes have spread 'spatially=laterally' to all cultures and evolve in complexity, are substituting and parasitizing the resources of the planet and a healthy, wealthy human organism where all citizens cells should have shelter, health-care, welfare goods and a Universal salary in ¥€\$ money to reproduce and consume life goods they need to survive. Instead a different superorganism of machines, the metal-earth is born. And it will, once its AI robots with solar skins reproduced in automated 3D printing company-mothers no longer need us, eliminate our species. But this is NOT explained because animetal idol-ogies are 'imprinted' emotionally since infancy by repetition in the past through segregational religions and nationalist mantras, today through audiovisual fictions that disaggregate people from each other making them addicted to the consumption=vitalization of machines – no longer needed to work as AI robots start the Final Solution (no labor, human obsolescence). Only then the 'verbal, informative nervous network' that in all healthy superorganisms control the blood and defensive systems could save us, in praxis and theory: social scientists as political regulating with laws to the benefit of man the other networks. But they are corrupted. Capitalist democracies are placebo systems, created by Company-mothers in Holland and UK and US (tea party revolution) by lawyers of corporations that doubled as politicians to sell laws to companies of weapons (right wing parties) and consumption companies (left wing parties) as they DON'T issue money but tax-farm humans and pander to financiers. While true social scientists are censored by FMasters with fiction, hate memes and lack of distribution in metal-networks of communication. And citizens cannot vote pain messages as in true Greek democracies to punish politicians and Stockrats, owners of corporations protected by immunity and S.A. Laws. This is the bleak picture of the future of mankind which at this st-age only a humanist r=evolution of FMasters who cared to survive till the 7th generation could abort. But their history show they are experts only in greed, hate memes against life and suicide. **Ideal History: the reform of the wor(l)d.***

The supœrganism of mankind designed with its 'economic frame of reference' that value goods according to their Whealth = biologic utility to foster the drives of life humans need to thrive and survive; controlling with \pm prices its production. The same laws that apply to the study on how cells becomes wholes through its connection through physiologic networks, of energy, reproduction and information, apply to the way humans are organized by energetic territories, economic, re=productive networks and informative, cultural, legal networks.

The Universe was on reason (max. i) + love (max. Δ)= Δi ; so **it** would be easy to cre(dit)ate ideal, immortal history: a world ruled by 'social doctors' that use the 'isomorphic' laws of efficient Universal organisms to make History immortal and the 99% thrive, evolving from its present 'worm' state that poisons with lethal goods its cells, into an efficient mammal where they get welfare goods, freedom and just nervous laws. But the greedy worm works on e-motion and hate... So a r=evolution needs +3 -3 positive and negative reforms of global defensive, economic and legal wor(l)d systems:

\pm measures from the memetic & immunologic systems, which must promote life goods, health-care and human languages of information and sciences while on the negative side should forbid lethal technologies that kill our body, poison our mind (weapons, fiction & hate memes) or compete and atrophy them in labor and war fields (robots, software).

\pm measures from the eco(nomic)system to enhance the reproduction of welfare goods and limit the production of lethal goods.

- measure: All company-mothers of machines&weapons split shares giving them to governments for a 50% 'stockratic' control keeping its private management, so civilinations can regulate, promote, forbid or reform the productive system.

+ measure: all supœrganisms distribute for free to all its cells a universal energy salary in oxygen to kick out production and consumption of welfare goods. So to create a just, democratic demand economy the 7 civilinations will send to every human in a world crypocurrency a monthly a ¥€\$ salary of 1000 1 euro=1 dollar = 100 yens = 5 yuans, used as a NO-debt language to consume & reproduce the welfare goods of the 'ethonomic' frame of reference, ending poverty, immigration and readdressing production to cater only human needs and terraform the Earth to the image & likeness of mankind.

- measure to create a true democracy: The Informative, legal system should judge=vote *a posteriori* with pain messages politicians who don't serve thoe goals, as cells do with a brain that harms them.

+ measure: Nations construct an efficient 5D scalar, social system by devolving to regions enhanced welfare administrations, while reducing national animetal parasitic structures (armies, financial systems) upgrading them to a unified human system of the 7 civilinations of mankind, with EU like common networks forming an heptarchy, guide by the Human Constitution of a Healthy whealthy body of history: Max. Human goods = Min lethal goods policed and suppressed by the military.

The result will be immortal History where 'the 3rd age of time with an excess of lethal information that brings entropy=death is reversed, setting the equation of the 3 ages of Earth backwards with history as its eternal present: Gaia<History<Metal-earth.

Such system could be implemented if our political, financial & Academic elites understood rationally and ethically history, as the organism of all mankind and its role as the efficient neuronal people-caste that must serve its body, the 90% and repress the lethal metalife species that will destroy as, as it is simply and ideal immortal supœrganism of History that imitates Nature's efficient supœrganisms from physical systems that 'bathe' all its atoms in ¥-monetary energy and synchronize its motions with the same informative gravitational= just legal language sto all biologic systems that synchronize its cell motions with simultaneous nervous=legal messages and give all cells free energy=oxygen. Even an agreement of the 3 leading political nations, Mr. POTUS, Mr EU & Mr. China could make it happen. But we don't live in ideal History; but doe to the praxis of Animetal idol-ogies we live in the age extinction of mankind by a rival species, lethal technologies backed by animetal memes. So a resurrection and reform of History's physiological networks to build that perfect organism is nowhere to be seen. So unfortunately we must return to the facts of the Extinctive, Entropic Age of Animetals, explained from the p.o.v of machines.

THE 3 AGES OF EARTH: VORTEX OF TIME HISTORY WITHIN GAIA, ITS LARGER SUPœRGANISM

What is the future of history, the super organism of Mankind developed in time, from the first mitochondrial eve, who was able to speak and multiplied all over the Earth, making the homo sapiens the collective mind of the planet; to the last human beings who will exit Earth when a new more intelligent species displaces ours from our present top predator position?

As we are just part of a larger supœrganism, Earth, it is logic to consider 1st how evolution shapes the future of the whole planet in which our smaller, shorter existence takes place.

The founding father of geology, James Hutton invented the word super organism precisely to define the Earth's slow geological cycles. He recommended physiology as the science to study hydrology likening the rivers of Gaia to veins that shape the body of the Earth and carry its nutritious elements to its living cells, animals and forests that gather on its sides. Gaia's veins merely have slower annual rhythms in his crop production, compared to the daily circulation of nutrients in our blood that feed and reproduce the cells of the body, according to the metric law of the scalar, 'fifth dimension' of the universe, which states that the bigger a system is in space, the slower the clock cycles of its physiological reproductive networks and informative, evolutionary ages will be. This means that if we put at fast motion, the geological and physiological cycles of the Earth the planet will seem to us alive; and vice versa if we slow down the metabolic cycles of a smaller cell they will resemble us those of a factory either reproducing the goods the biological or social supœrganism needs to survive. Super organisms co-

exist in different scales thanks to the 'metric of the scalar fifth dimension' of parts which are faster and code with more information, larger beings which are slower and provide energy to its parts. Mankind is not alone in this planet, not it is in command of Earth, as so many ego centered humans think, but we are part of the planet and that poses some serious questions about our role on its evolution as a supœrganism of a larger scale, illustrated in the graphs.

Destroy the re=productive placentas of GNA extinctive species: Kill the child before it becomes a tiger hunter.

Survival is ruled by a simple law: As more individuals of each species are born than can survive; consequently, there is a struggle for existence" Darwin. How all this applies to the 3 ages of Earth as supœrganism in which History exists? Simple: *Earth also evolves increasing its information and as History lives within it, it suffers its consequences, both positive (evolution of life) and negative (evolution of lethal goods, weapons that kill us).*

The repetitive WAR cycles that kill History are vortex of accelerated evolution of lethal metal-information that preys on man. Earth's surface is its 'informative membrain' that evolves and absorbs its information from the outer world-universe in which the point exist – in the case of the Earth, absorbs and evolves the light bits of information provided by the sun. So Life is everything as Earth is a supœrganism, whose surface-mind is made of smaller supœrganisms - living beings. Complexity talks of different forms of atomic 'life' as systems that use light to obtain energy & information in increasing degrees of strength and complexity. So after simpler anaerobic age, the age of plants used light only as energy, the age of animals also as information and now the third Earth evolves into light-mechanisms, robots with solar skins and optic minds. They will complete the 3 horizon of Earth's evolution guided by 'animetals', visual humans slaves of metal-memes 'who believe don't reason' and cannot control its desire for higher metal-power even at the risk of killing their sons till the 'seventh generation', unless rational humans impose a scientifically-managed super organism of history on top of the metal-Earth.

We shall go back and forth through all those texts studying different elements in geographical space (Civilinations) time ages, Languages of social power (money, weapons and words), and its memes, entropic ages of war and destruction and its cyclical patterns for both superorganisms, History and the Metal-earth, mostly with a simplified model of 5D laws, but without renouncing ever to the truths of humanism (D of the scientific method), warning against entropic extinction (E), showing cyclical, biological patterns and rescuing accurate data today censored by political and economical correctness and the Company-mothers of machines of information and its FMAsters (financial-media-academia masters) that print with them the digital money, audiovisual information and authorized 'fairy tales' about history and mankind that defend their 3 ideologies.

1st some quotes on the duality of our suicidal cultures v. the truths of love & intelligence of the 5D World

Quotes on 5 D History vs. Animal, parasitic & Genocidal idol-ogies.

"I have written with a profound love for my own country, but as I advance in life, I grow more simple, and I become more and more patriotic for humanity." Hugo on God= supærganism of History

"Our current morality has grown on the soil of the ruling tribes and castes." Nietzsche; on animal idol-ogies

'Love each other as I have loved you' Jesus, on the arrow of social evolution of the 5th dimension.

"Let me issue and control a Nation's money and I care not who makes her laws. The few who could understand the system will either be so interested in its profits, or so dependent on its favors, that there will be no opposition from that class, while on the other hand, the great body of the people mentally incapable of comprehending the tremendous advantage that capital derives from the system, will bear its burdens without complaint, and perhaps without even suspecting that the system is inimical to their interests."

Amschel Rothschild, Leading financier of the British Empire 1838, on the essence of parasitic, financial capitalism.

'Technological civilization is programmed by the principle that something ought to be done because it is technologically possible. If it is possible to build nuclear weapons, they must be done, even if they might destroy us all. Once this principle is accepted, humanist Values (something has to be done because it is needed by man) are Dethroned and technological development becomes the foundation of ethics'. Fromm, father of political psychology. On the essence of Mechanism.

'I had a nightmare. I dreamt with a man who asked me to give him Crispr CAS-9. He was Hitler.'

Jen Doudna, rewarded with the 2020 Nobel for her discovery of Cas-9, the molecule bacteria use to edit viruses - the system most likely used anonymously to edit the coronavirus out of 3 parts - so we know, 'viral genedit must be done'.

'Capitalism is the astounding belief that the wickedest of all people, will do the wickedest of all things (killing mankind without credit for welfare goods, as financiers monopolize the issue of money to re=produce the goods of maximal profit: weapons & hate memes) for the common Good' Keynes on the cause of industrial wars; so we know 'wars must be done'.

'If we produce Alpha MACHOs, stable strange matter on Earth, they'll accumulate in the planet center, triggering an ice-9 reaction making Earth into a 15 Km strangelet.' Wilczek, rewarded with a Physics Nobel Prize, after his discovery of the ice-9 reaction, rehearsed by the Industry of accelerators he defends in genocidal suits so we know 'ice-9 must be done'

Quotes on 5D Universe vs. mechanist, creationist idol-ogies.

'Only entropy comes easy' Chekhov. 'No one is more hated than the man who speaks the truth' Plato.

"A human being is part of the whole, called by us 'Universe'; a part limited in time and spatial information. He experiences himself, his thoughts and feelings as something separated from the rest -- a kind of optical delusion of his consciousness."

Einstein, on the entangled forest man cannot see - and its pentalogic elements, 'space', 'time', 'scales' of parts and wholes, 'entropic limits', and 'languages of the mind'

'0ε (finitesimal mind mirror) x ∞ Universe = 'constant I-World': Equation of any mind.

I=Eye (Topologic space) > Wor(I)d = (Cyclical Time): Equation of the Humind.

Every mind is a point of view that perceives only with languages that mirror a reduced world it confuses with the whole Universe, placing itself at the center, reason why each mind is a subjective ego. In the past when man only spoke words, we thought God 'created by naming things' in Arab or Hebrew, the language of creation. Today after man learned mathematics, he believes God, mind of the Universe speaks only with numbers and truth ends in a price or equation

7 CIVILINATIONS OF MANKIND. GLOBALIZATION OF THE ANGLO-AMERICA.

Let us inquire then in more detail, this 3rd perspective, worth to study in History, the memetic, *scalar*, cultural view.

Genes in history have a limited importance, circumscribed to the 3 genders and 3 'mental languages' of mankind, deeply rooted in the ternary structure of organisms, its topologies and languages. So the white dolichocephalic man is visual likely with a higher crossing of visual lineal White Neanderthal people, as we advanced 30 years ago when not even the idea of genetic crossing was considered. So he has a lineal view of time and did become earlier on hypnotized by the visual glare of gold that imitates the sun color and made of lineal iron its entropic weapon of choice. His worldview is spatial, literalist, its art realist. It is the quintessential macho man we will criticize in higher measure in those papers, as it is bringing humanity into destruction. So it has dominated the earlier violent Paleolithic and the last, 3rd metallic age of History, inventing most lethal technologies.

The Mongoloid is brachicephalic, with a higher development of verbal, time languages; which communicate humans socially. So he built organic peaceful societies with a higher social harmony. Accordingly he developed a cyclical, organic view of time epitomized in the Taoist view of yin-information & yang, entropy that combine to reproduce ∞ beings and saw a vital Universe. It was born probably through neoteny (childish maturity) in the Himalayans to maximize survival on harsh conditions, which is a key process of informative enhancing evolution in the Universe.

Finally the Black psylocephalic mind with a 'higher emotional and motor axis' is the artistic, empathic culture of mankind, corresponding to the female gender; in close communion with animist Nature; the Earth of life, Gaia.

We can then easily divide geographically those cultures in 7 civilinations, broken artificially by tribal, military men, which define the symmetries of the 5D hyperbolic scalar dimension of the Universe: $T \perp S > \Delta \pm j$: The 3 ages of History, Earth & its social scales:

Gaia: Paleolithic (Black Africa) < Indonasia & Asia: Mongoloid: Neolithic > Metal: 800 cycles: Semite Islam & Latin America > 80 years Industrial cycles: Europe & Anglo-America, which are the white visual 'animetal cultures' that have become globalized.

There is however a fundamental difference between Europe and Anglo-America, the 2 cultures where I spent most of my life, which we shall stress throughout all the papers on History, as it is the key difference between the duality of futures of mankind.

While ideally humanity should have remained in a present, welfare Neolithic world with a few positive machines in balance with Gaia, we have become a culture of machines. However Europeans due to the influence of its foundational Greek>Latin rational, humanist, artistic democratic culture, has tried through its r=evolutionary periods and higher minds to control lethal machines and put man above metal, by considering the human natural language, the spatial I=Eye>Time Wor(l)d, with its syntax that makes man the center of reality: Man (subject) > verb (action) > Object (energy of the subject), in its social expression, the law, above money, a digital language that reduces and compares man (salary) = (Price) Object. The Anglo-American culture rejects this view and as the founder of capitalism considers money above law even if it maintains a placebo structure of democracy. This difference has its origin in two different 'religions'=beliefs. Anglo-America is born in the Hebrew tradition of the old testament, an earlier fetish go(l)d culture from the bronze age, while Europe always gave more importance to the reform of the Gospel based in social love and after the French and Russian R=evolutions returned to a rational view of mankind with the law above money and after II world war rejected also the nationalist worship of weapons. So belief vs. reason, worship of metal either in its informative go(l)d form (capitalism that puts money above the law), organic form (machines and technoutopia, discovered in the Anglo-American civilization) and weapons (nationalism) differentiated after II W.W. both cultures which means Anglo-America believes in metal ideologies and will continue evolving lethal technologies till they extinguish mankind, while the European Union and the other 5 cultures believe in humanism and could have implemented a control of the tree of metal. But Anglo-America is the culture that became globalized in the digital era, so the welfare State and humanism of Europe also fades away. The question then is who and what kind of memetic culture Anglo-America is 'selling to the world' through its information machines that print e-money, audiovisual fiction and 'Academia'. What we call the FMAsters (Financial-Media-Academia masters), since obviously the truth of an economic ecosystem ruled by company-mothers of machines terraforming the earth to the image and likeness of its offspring, with complete disregard of human rights and values, as an object, compared and replaced in search for profits by fast

evolving robots and computers suites and autonomous weapons CANNOT be sold. The answer is a series of wishful thinking, caring political and economically correct placebos that pretend to be humanist and often disguise the culture as European, when its origin and evolution comes from a different world.

Specifically Anglo-America has a 'hierarchical social structure' based in race, history and financial wealth, dominated by the original Hebrew culture of go(l)d banker priests that monopolize the industry of information machines, since the age of the press, when it regressed the gospel culture of love to the segregational memes of the Hebrew press; imposed the Ham damnation of slavery; invented stock companies and monopolized from the City and Wall Street the reproduction of money inventing in Holland and UK after the glorious revolution, the industrial world. This society triumphed over the military Germanic version after a series of internecine wars for industrial profits, first against the 'inferior' colored species of the Ham Damnation, then when the world was conquered to keep the profits of military industries between 'cousins' (the Russian, German and British 'emperors') and then between 'mestizo' Jewish-Germanic dynasties of bankers and military men (Churchill Jerome, Rosenfelt=Roosevelt, Hitler 'Frankenheimer', Goring Epenstein). Greek-Latin Europe could only regain its concept of a humanist welfare world after the tragic death of 100 million people in those II world wars. But now we are back again to the same mixture of Germanic military and Jewish go(l)d beliefs, shrewdly hidden those brutal values with placebo fictions, while both animetal cultures together develop from America through its corporations a future for machines over humanity and beliefs over reason. But all this is disguised by a censorship of political and economical correctness that hides the real structure of power of its society, imprinted by the Goebbels' method of repetition of lies its beliefs as if it were social science. We talk of a 'frozen' structure of social science fictions that please the ego of man as the supreme being of the Universe, with a lineal manifest destiny carried through machines; just because they 'make money'. So we can *consider the future settled unless the system is reformed. Since humans have no other role in that culture that caters for the 1% of managers and owners of companies and for its machines that to consume=vitalize and re=produce them, working on those companies. But those jobs are now replaced by robots with AI minds, soon with solar skins, independent of man, due to the global warming placebo activism. So the middle working class is displaced and fast loose its way of life. But the elites won't care. Since the mind frame of these financial 'chosen races' is primitive in its madness: to monopolize the issue of money, disguise its power, defend its apartheid segregational 'other nation' and ignore all the problems of humanity – not our problem – as go(l)d will provide through the evolution and reproduction of machines and weapons. A resurgence of old ideologies, abrahamic religions, nationalism, capitalism, covered with fictions and a growing infantilism as audiovisual minds erase the verbal reasoning of people, is heralded as culture. Above all as mankind enters its 'entropic age' of dissolution of social structures and the metal-kind organizes in networks of perfect efficiency, 'egocy' (Ego=idiocy) disguises as freedom a chaotic state of individual powerlessness of humanity. Since the organic networks of our species are becoming controlled by company-mothers.*

The solution? More of the same: to hide this tragic destiny in the making our FMAsters just repeat ad nauseam their schemes of global anoxia (lack of credit for mankind as all money is siphoned to speculation), mass-media selfie fictions (each human a Truman Show in Facebook), while 'Academia' keeps prizing techno-utopia. This year the winners of the Nobel prize of chemistry were the people that found the molecule bacteria use to edit virus and enhanced its capabilities so all biochemists knew a virus could be edited to create a pandemic. But as we 'must believe in technology and the superiority of man' with its lineal manifest destiny and hide the real structure of our society dominated by company-mothers terraforming the world for its machines that make money four our elite of stockrats whose culture segregates them from mankind, all criticism is rejected. Even the existence of a hierarchy of financial and corporative power above the law of democracies and its \$elected politicos is rejected with victimist fictions and deviated to emotional hate memes and censorship (holocaust industry, trash Tv/internet.) The globalized Anglo-America culture 'believes' and will do so till the end. So there is zero argument on the future, zero analysis of social organisms with scientific models as we do in those of those papers, and our 'religious' social structures are considered 'the only' possible system, in which we must believe till the end.

We analyze from the perspective of the scientific ABC+D-E method the duality of humanist welfare democracies vs. placebo 'stockracies' – the 2 set of memes that define the 2 futures of mankind – one immortal history, fading away into entropy.

Vatican... It does NOT need, and certainly is NOT a presence so complex as that of a human life organism – the most complex of them all, which ego science considers the only organism – one of the reasons of 5D rejection as in 5D an organic system only requires a herd of similar beings and from them there will always emerge an organization from the simplest hunting herd to the more complex mammal.

The immediate consequence of the fundamental law of survival in super organisms able to overcome extinction through the evolution of social systems into larger wholes, which is the ultimate mandate of the universe of fractal parts and wholes, is the foundation in solid grounds of the science of history and the purpose of religions, whose aim is to imitate the logic laws of the universe in the construction of such supœrganisms.

The brain is imprinted in earlier age with software networks - ideological memes - that allow the human to act as a whole society, and those common ideas of eusocial love and the books of revelation are the informative network we call God:

In the graph, a love god, express a complex program of eusocial evolution proper of all organic species. So those who love will act with other humans creating social networks that share energy and information, the 2 parameters of the universe. It does not matter so much the literal details of the 'DNA-program' of a religion of love (Christianity or Buddhism or socialism) but the 'biological, survival strategy' of eusocial love. So prophets adapt the concept of love to the 'specific' jargons of each culture. What matters is to create the social mind - the fact that love creates a simultaneous desire to share energy and information and evolve into social super-organisms, which are the 'subconscious collective' mystique gods of our religions - not the creators of the universe but an earlier version of the word 'nation' (tribal religions) or 'Humanity' (oikoumene religions). Hence the use here as synonymous words the concepts of god, Humanity and history - the life of the supœrganism of Mankind from its first verbal cell to the last man who will speak.

In the graph we show the meaning of religions, the subconscious collective of human super organisms of history and its natural evolution in scales of growing size, which ideally would enclose all mankind, loose its 'mystical hang-ups' and become studied in history just a precursors of the laws of love of the social 5th dimension, both in its study of the anthropomorphic super organisms of mankind (western religions of social love) an the universal super organisms and its taoist laws of timespace arrows (eastern religions): the 6 main human cultures born of the natural evolution of the concept of social love and its super organisms of mankind and the Universe (western vs. eastern gods). From the graph we can get an obvious conclusion: tribal religions and tribal 'nationalisms', two expressions of the same concept which believe their 'god/nation' is the 'only/best' one are just a primitive version of the larger organic view of modern systemic sciences. And today a mere excuse to foster the evolution of weapons that will kill us.

For that reason the evolution of tribal religions ended in oikoumene love religions and finally socialist doctrines. While the evolution of animist and taoist cults became the final horizon of systems sciences with their organic models of a living Universe, this writer develop when working in science at the turn of the century. In brief, we can again apply the Correspondence principle of science to account for religions as evolutionary stages of an Organic Theory of Everything applied to human cultures or the Universe as super organisms.

We can then easily distinguish the Age of 'Neolithic' Religions of the Living Organic Universe, which continued in Africa & Asia in 3 Ages: Animist age, when every living organism on Earth was giving a living soul; Taoist, Buddhist age when a more profound metaphysical analysis of the entanglement of those souls brought about the understanding of the principles of 5D scalar organisms in verbal thought, and the 3rd age of those texts with a deep scientific understanding.

While in the west anthropomorphic organisms of history were considered Gods that evolved in 3 ages:

- The animetal age of tribal, genetic racist religions (Judaism and Hinduism, being the paradigm) based in the power of go(l)d and iron people-castes on top of an oppressed humanity, evolved through the 5D social force of love into:
- Oikoumene religions in which humanity as a whole became the 'social God' (Christianity, Islam), and its creation was expressed, first through the mystery of trinity, the language, the wor(l)d that became man (the prophet) and spread the common DNA-memetic message of love to all humans so they could share energy and information to create a global superorganism, mind of Earth; and then as the relationship between the $\Delta-1$ and $\Delta+1$ scales of a lanwave was not understood in Islam, the message was simplified but the sacredness of the Word and the message of charity and social love kept. To evolve

finally in its 3rd age of R=evolutionary religions which appeared in the Industrial r=evolution with the goal of controlling the metal-earth, its company-mothers and machines for the benefit of a single equalitarian mankind.

So while religions express some of the whys of social evolution in old jargons, *ideally they would be taught as stages in the search for the understanding of the organic nature of everything in scientific terms.* The experience of creation of a human God is mental, informative and the network might be gravito-magnetic, gravitational, a quantum potential, or just induced in each brain by a common verbal message, which creates the 5D effect of 'simultaneity' of information that makes emerge a new plane of existence. We do not know. But as believers feel it, it must exist, even if as gravitation is an invisible force, but as it has effects on mass, it must exist.

As to when it is formed according to 5D, the commonest duality of organisms in the interplay of $\Delta-1$, Δ , parts and wholes is the cycle of internal maximal 'activity' with the external system in stillness, and external maximal activity with the internal system ad minimal. In humans this S-T beat is the sleep-awakening cycle. When we sleep externally we are immobile and internally we have maximal activity. *As we are externally immobile in $\Delta+1$, then an external simultaneous network with synchronous motion of all its parts; that is all believers at the same distance cruising with Earth through space takes place. This is the only fact required for a higher emergent 5D plane to take root in any scale. So the pre-condition happens in the dream state, in much larger number of believers as most are in a contiguous time zone; and in smaller reunions of synchronous motions as the circling at Kaaba or the view of the Pope speaking at Vatican. A similar less interesting effect happens in concerts hearing some virtual 3rd rate poet, enhanced by industrial mechanic sounds.*

But a language can be negative, destructive as today are metal-communicators spreading hate memes and as they project its actions in reality mankind suffers a process of self-destruction through 'fiction hate memes' justified by evilwood because fiction is supposed NOT to influenc the actions of people. Of course it does, as all mirror languages do.

Neo-Paleolithic final, negative childish age of mankind.

So we talk with the arrival of metal-communicators that spread hate memes, since the age of the Press of a new anti-religious age of destruction of human social love, parallel to the devolution of collective mankind by those metal-communicators:

- The age of the press and its hate memes that regressed the social evolutionary age of love religions to the Hebrew Bible with its segregational memes and go(l)d fetish mantras. The Ham Damnation of the Hebrew bible imposed modern slavery.
- The age of the yellow press that expanded hate memes against the colored people and created colonialism, following the expansion of the biblical HAM culture that started its globalization of its simplistic mechanist view of the world.
- The age of hate radio that brought fascism to Europe as military Germanic leaders transformed Germany in a war machine.
- The age of hate tv and Internet in which we live now that expanded islamophobia, techno-utopia and degraded human beings back to an individual selfie neoplaeolithic age.

Below a 30 years old graph, on the future now present childish 'neo-Paleolithic' violent, disaggregated mind of mankind, our millennial. Humans, regressed to a violent age of null understanding of social organisms. The problem though is that 'children are the staple food' of the Darwinian Universe. So as we come closer to GNA-extinction, our attitude is more infantile.

The last generations of mankind in the more advanced regions of the metal-earth, become unconnected from the ethic networks of its historic supærganisms, they no longer know about. So they connect to the virtual networks of the metal-earth, reaching 'the unbearable lightness of being post-human'. As in the parable of matrix they prefer NOT to know what is reality - so the chances to make them r=evolve reality into a human world becomes impossible.

As the cells of a body supærganism, they feast in the freedom of rigor mortis, absorbing greedily all the goodies available. As A.I. takes over most of its tasks, they become infantile, selfie, body-oriented. We can resume those last 'decade' generations: My generation X, the 'slackers', still wondered and talked about the no-future. They why generation is fully immersed into the

BED BUG PREPARE FOR FEEDING.
Saliva is injected, containing an anesthetic to reduce pain, and an anticoagulant to keep blood flowing.

The last leader of tv-hate ...

THE CELEB APPRENT
18 wild cards.
One Trump

Parasites inject anesthetics to inhibit defense systems as Financial-Media System of informative machines do with fiction & hate media to inhibit defense against the financial & corporative monopoly in the issue of money that chokes mankind off credit

virtual reality, the millennial...the zero generation will be so expendable as the jobs they don't have, and won't need it, addict to virtual reality, living of a Universal salary, waiting for its 'disconnection' - the end of 'cogito ergo sum', as the birth of the chip homoctonos defines a finale, which only a humanist r=evolution could halt.

In the graph, the span of all the generations of the Neo-Paleolithic, which is the age of digital visual thought, the age of America, between II world war and the robotic era:

- Those born in 1940s, the **Victor Generation**, the last humans in full command of its machines.
- Baby Boomers, the **We Generation** of hippies, as visual mental machines started to take over, refocused on the body, falling into social dissolution, back in time to the NEO-NEOLITHIC of Goddesses of fertility and shamanic cults
- My **X-Generation** of slackers, the last 'intelligent' human beings, able to 'Cogito ergo sum', but with decreasing energy to organize a true r=evolution, overwhelmed by the growing noise of audiovisual mass-media information
- **¥-generation**, millennial kids NO longer able to form meaningful human networks, as they become attached to virtual screens, the first neo-Paleolithic people visually programmed to belief, in the age of 'I see, Credo ergo sum'.

- **Zero generation**, no more to go, born with the pandemic 'global internet jail, will be like Data in Matrix, preferring to live a 3D virtual reality, passive actors of the rise of AI self-driving machines – to die after the 2070s crashes that will mutate those AI robots into a war ecosystem of automated 3D printing company-mothers like ant-hills.

In the graph, from 92 'extinction of man', we have gone through the paces of the foreseen devolution of Mankind, first away from logic thought into the revivalism of nationalisms, as social structures went down the ladder, past the heights of ethic social thought both mystical (oikoumene religions) and scientific (socialism, humanism). We then entered into the magic, emotional era, and most humans abandoned even the attachment to tribal groups.

Today at the head of the wave of robotics, metal-minds and internet, Americans are clearly regressing since the chip was invented in the 70s in every scale of humanism, entering an 'age of pure entropy' and dissolution of all human structures shown in the next graph, now globalized - what I call the Neo-Paleolithic, as we are made obsolete by machines - and yet not a single scholar can accept that technology competes and degrades man:

The graph is key to understand our present degradation as a species that does not speak better than machines in digital terms, and only equal to emotional 'animals' in visual ones. So by rejecting our verbal, logic thought, our higher asset, and becoming 'stupid', we are destroying any future we might have.

But the bottom line of this process is obvious: Humans are increasingly obsolete as capitalist software is translating all the actions humans performed for machines in the past. So Enzymen ARE NO LONGER NEEDED, as we graphed 20 years ago in the capitalist pyramid of the then future XXI c. where humans would be just attached to virtual machines and robots will make their job. That is the age we enter now, predicted 30 years ago - a time of deconstructionism, visual Neo-Paleolithic violence, and 'credo ergo sum', knee-jerk reaction zero-zombie people.

But all deaths feed the evolution of a new top predator species, the AI machine we called then the 'chip homoctonos', which is educated with 'visual violent video games', its imagination, it will like to 'make real' hunting human targets, once it takes over our only 2 jobs, in labor and war fields as consumers=vitalizers of machines and workers=reproducers in its automated company-mothers to increase the profits of the 0.002% of stockrat billionaires.

The wisdom of entropic-death-happy processes, releasing 'locally' the citizens-cells of societies.

A final hurdle for mankind to understand 5D social sciences is the IQless, local short term memoriless stage of entropic death: Cells, atoms or citizens living in a corrupted, dying 'flat brain' world where the informative, nervous, ethic, just legal system has collapsed 'releases' its citizens-cells into chaos=freedom which gives 'pleasure' as a void of social consciousness allows a dog-eat-dog society to seek for selfish immediate reward. The *higher social plane of existence that extracted energy* from the individual 'homo bacteria' is gone and the I-selfie mind REDUCES its intelligence to short term time cycles, local territories and cannot even conceive the existence of 'organic scales', symbiotic love, strength of the whole, synchronous, simultaneous motions. Mankind is entering that free-chaotic stage where ONLY company-mothers who are evolving inversely into a perfect global organism managed by AI-suites, computers, robots and company-mothers with unlimited flow of money do all the work so humans become ever more dependent on the machines that atrophy its minds (iphones), work for them and have nothing but egocy (ego=idiocy) left, tyrants of a rising, evolving wave of AI telepathic mechanisms that as weapons can easily kill them. *The process of destruction of the higher social scales of mankind as an organism is thus parallel to the rise of a superorganism of machines, the re=productive company-mother, which monopolized the languages of human power, weapons (gunboats), bills of money (making stock paper tender legal money with unlimited rights to reproduce it) and bills of law, when it established placebo democracies in Holland, UK & US, whose politicos were lawyers of the company dedicated to issue laws for its products, NOT for mankind, which suffered ever since anoxia (lack of credit), all disguised by a placebo polling (Presidents are not elected but \$elected) Roosevelt, which metal-communicators' fiction SOMA disguises as freedom.*

The cycles of the Animetal, Anglo-American culture.

The graph shows the cycles of the industrial r=evolution as a new national generation substitutes a previous one, on top of the evolution of the metal-earth. Those generations also bring the nation that finds the new energy to the top predator status of history. Because energy is also the substance of which weapons are made.

- Thus, we had an English age of steam machines, between 1780s and 1857, followed by a crisis of overproduction of steam machines and stock-money that brought the 1857 ±8/9 years product cycle crashes of the train-based economy.
- From 1857 to 1929, we lived the age of electro-chemical energies, machines and chemical explosives, dominated by

During the Industrial Revolution, a new nation and its 3 generations of engineers, discoverers of the new machine & energy of the cycle, become the founding fathers, industrial reproducers and decadent warriors of nationalistic wars, carrying the evolution of the machine to its military completion... Now in the Singularity Age, machines becomes organic, so we make self-feeding bombs, and if we survive them, self-reproductive factories (nano bacteria) and Robot life

Germany, followed by a crisis of overproduction of cars and radios, which caused the 1929 crash, 72 years after the train crash.

So Germany declared war to the world with gas, tanks and bombers to keep profits going and US followed suit.

- It came then the III cycle of electronic machines, electronic money and Nuclear Bombs that took place from 1929-2001, the age of America; which again ended in the dotcom and mortgage crashes, 72+8/9 years after 1929:

Followed by the Singularity Age, the last Cycle of machine Evolution dominated by robots, solar energy and China. Scientists call the birth of Artificial Intelligence, the Singularity age, when robots, which can use solar energy to become autonomous will complete the evolution of machines as organic forms, automating factories & expelling most human workers and soldiers from labor and war fields, as previous revolutions did with obsolete III World non-technological humans, unless we forbid legally their evolution. Money, likely a cryptocurrency independent of man, will become then the digital informative, 'memetic code' that organizes their reproduction in those automated company-mothers.

The 'company-mothers' of those machines whose biological function is to evolve and re=produce them, made first the bodies of machines (XIX c.), then the minds of machines (cameras-eyes, mobile-ears and chips-brains. Finally, in the XXI century, as nature does with simple organisms, such as viruses in cells, where the 3 'parts' of the virus – its DNA information, body and legs are constructed – and then assembled together, we put together all those organic components into autonomous robots, completing the industrial r=evolution of 'metallife' – a new organic species, made of a stronger substance than carbon-life. Thus the industrial r=evolution is the evolution of 'metallife', in 3+1 phases, as we made 1st the bodies of machines, then hearts-engines, metal-minds and now we put them together in organic robots in the final r=evolution of machines. Thus Industrial humans become 'animetal enzymen', a biologic species that substitutes the old synapsid=verbal Homo Sapiens, because paradoxically enzymen have debased the ethic wor(l)d that creates a world to the image and likeness of man, always the subject of its sentences, which through verbal actions control objects, substituted by the digital language of machines and money used in an organic planet, to evolve another organic species with more complex metal atoms. *Why those cycles are so exact in the leading 'HAM' industrial culture has only an idol-ogical generation: the control of the Anglo-American civilination by stockrats, its company-mothers and idol-ogies of machine worship is absolute. So there is a superfluidity, with 0 resistance to the evolution of technology whatever it takes, including the life of millions of humans in war.*

Because company-mothers control the physiological networks of mankind (they reproduce its military systems, pay laws to politicians to favor its products, and reproduce most of the money), the Anglo-American biblical culture has been imitated in other nations without much difficulty by indoctrinating its old animetal warrior and banker elites with the mechanist doctrines.

It calls then attention that in all those nations, perfectly programmed to develop mechanisms and forget the destiny of mankind, the center of all the emotional and human discourse is the 'free individual'. This is one of the many paradoxes of complex organisms the 'egocentric human' can hardly understand: precisely because the 'system' of physiological networks has such an absolute control in the languages of power of society (and the people-castes that 'own them') the individual is left in a free, chaotic, entropic, competitive, Darwinian state, which is the 'field state' of any herd of preys it confuses with freedom. *It is also reduced in its consciousness to the entropic state of dog-eat-dog that he sees as the only way of being. This is the way of the American, but the reader should understand America is the mixture of all human cultures displaced into the technological future. So it is NOT a nation, but mankind into its final 'hour', its 'entropic' Tt-stage of 'not being' anymore mankind – but a mass of dissolved cells.* Today, In the age of the chip radiation, companies of information machines controlled by the HAM culture and its FMAsters (Financial-Media-Academia Masters), whose print e-money in monopoly in Wall Street, condemning to global anoxia the majority of mankind, imprint humans with hate and fiction memes through Hollywood and Internet corporations, devolving the collective subconscious to a neo-Paleolithic violent, emotional age and degrade science through academic think tanks and prize ceremonies to impose this mechanist, computer-based view upon the organic Universe under a false camouflage of humanism and political and economical correctness borrowed from the European, organic true culture of science, art and democracy those texts take to its next level of complexity; all because of the only obsessive purpose of its millenarian biblical go(l)d culture: to herd money, today by increasing corporative profits, through the reproduction and evolution of AI machines that displace humans from labor and war fields and terraform the Earth into the world of metal that will extinguish us. But that is a 'choice' their culture on top of the dominant nation of the world today, US, has done, it is NOT, we repeat the only deterministic no future of mankind but an imposition of the wrong memes of those who control the languages of social power of modern society. 'But those who impose truth with power will be the laugh of the Gods'. A.Einstein.

Stock phases

Financial brains: Guilder->Pound->Dollar->e-money

Body

Dutch->British Empire
Western World->
The Metal-Earth.

Last Verbal Empire: Iberia [Spain+Portugal]; 1588-1640

1 1640: Explosion of Iberia. Portugal and possessions become a satellite of England

1830's Opium mind's massacre: Bengali tea traders shift to 4 drug-sales. Hong-kong stock is created. 20??: it becomes dominant

1740: The tea Holocaust: After England conquers Bengala, 20 mill. peasants die of hunger, obliged to abandon rice crops for tea crops to lower tea price in London Stock 2

Till 1861: slaves are demanded according to cotton price in London. After war, they are substituted by machines. 3

THE MODERN WORLD: CAPITALIST DEMOCRACIES – HISTORY RULED BY COMPANY-MOTHER IN THE AGE OF THE MACHINE.

Company-mothers of weapons-machines conquered the world as they made obsolete companies of warriors. The last Human world empire, the Iberian conquistadors, strongest Human warriors, selected on the 800 arch of Animetal waves coming from Korea to Spain where the survivors learned to enjoy life had in tiny boats with a 10% survival rate created a global empire, which the Company of Gunboats, VOC easily erased from a tiny nation, Holland, within 2 decades. Such is the speed at which a new top predator reproductive species liquidates the mighty old 'dinosaur'. Then VOC migrated to London in 1688 in the glorious r=evolution with all the tools of the modern world, stock-markets to invent digital money speculating in shares, a central bank to print and legalize companies-money yellow press to print hate memes and money, artillery to kill at distance, slave workers as cargo and shipmen, a go(l)d biblical cult(ure) to money and segregational memes, and scientific racism, worship of technology, clocks to enslave human time to a salary, stockrats on top running faked democracies with a single war party, then split in a consumption one with the arrival of machines. The modern world was born and in 300 hundred years terraformed the Earth, prepared now for the age of robotics and 3 D automated factories of weapons and machines that will continue its biological reproductive radiation till the metal earth will be born...

Then everything changed to remain the same when In Venice, Galileo, the artillery master discovered ballistics and applied science to a lineal, mechanist model of the Universe. He improved canons and 'spyglasses', giving Venice the upper hand in sea combat with its 'lombardas'. The gunboat industry started and mass production in the arsenal of Venice created the first company, whose methods moved to Amsterdam, the Venice of the North, where the first stock-company was founded. Now a new form of money, printed paper money, a new form of 'information', hate memes (yellow press, Black Legend against the Habsburg king), and the Hebrew Bible, which got rid of the love social memes of the Gospel, stressing the segregation and go(l)d fetish culture of the old testament, came together in a new synergy of 'metal-networks' to the service of a new re=productive organism, the company-mother of machines and weapons, who will soon defeat all companies of warriors, take power in the nations of the Anglo-American civilization (Holland>Uk>US) establish a placebo system of bipartisan power with corporative lawyers doubling as politicians the service of corporations selling laws (representative democracies) and conquer the world within centuries, selling weappns colonial products and life cargo, making humans slaves for a price.

Legal & economic structure of company-mother, the new top predator Earth's organism. Its control of networks.

Why company-mothers rule the world has to do with history and the structure of social organisms, which are made of 'physiological' networks. So to control a society you just need to control its defensive=military, financial=economical, legal=political network and informative=memetic cultural network. And to do so historically you just need to reproduce and monopolize the issue of weapons, money and laws, the weaker 'human verbal side' of the equation, imposed by military power or bought with money. In this manner company-mothers of machines and weapons, able to reproduce without limit legal tender 'stock-paper', became dominant of all the languages of 'real network power' of human societies and established earlier in the XVII c. its power in Holland and UK, then in US, by imposing a submissive political system 'capitalist democracies', where its lawyers doubled as politicians and produce a stream of laws in favor of its products. *It is important to understand this history because 'modern corrupted democracies that don't serve the people but company-mothers were INVENTED by them, NOT the other way around.* First companies were born, then took power from kings and then they establish as a 'placebo' system of social freedoms without ever relinquish their control of the true networks of social power, its military, financial, informative and legal networks. And this was done efficiently because 'machines' reproduced those metal-memes of power much faster than humans. I.e. weapons kill humans not the other way around; information machines reproduced since the press age to the internet era news much faster than mouth to mouth; and they print money. So an organic system, which is the true 'organism' that is displacing Gaia and History appeared on Earth: The Financial-Media (informative machines, head of the metal-earth) > Military-Industrial Complex (body of energy and entropic machines). This IS the REAL ORGANISM of power of this planet, for whom MANKIND toils unending hours for a salary and politicians create laws for. While a placebo, friendly but powerless system call democracies enacts a theatrical game of 'polling' of \$elected presidents (presidents are \$elected not elected, said Roosevelt) for people to have a 'catharsis' in its theatrics. And all this works because mass-media companies, information machines, what we call the FMAsters, Financial-Media-Academia elite defends the system and does not let any other system or even a critical assessment of human reality surface beyond small individual groups. The outcome then is the world we live in – a world terraformed to the image and likeness of the networks of machines that conform the superorganism of the 'metal-earth' that is killing life and history at a growing speed.

The mathematical equations of classic capitalism that define the 'Financial-Media/Military-Industrial superorganism'.

It is worth to put in mathematical equations, as it is the language of companies and its owners, the process of creation of the metal-earth and the different ways in which the process is viewed by the two 'level's of scientific analysis – the level of the owners of those companies 'stockrats', financiers that won the right to print the money of society in the earlier st-ages of the Industrial "HAM culture', taking it from kings and parliaments through paper-money systems; and the *much higher level of biological organisms, for which the 'money' of corporations is just a digital language of re=production of its goods.*

- *For stockrats, the modern aristocrats all is about the monopolistic rights over the language of social power, money, as aristocrats had it over the old language of weapons, which they carried and could use, with no consequences, judged by aristocratic courts – today stockrats are protected by anonymous societies and produce in companies 90% of the global e-money... So they just care to play financial schemes to print money for free, or sell the goods of maximal prize to make profits that happen to be top predator weapons, or those of minimal cost to reproduce, 'mass-media waves of information' and that is what they do in the dominant 3 companies of capitalism, financial, media and military companies that represent the bulk of the economy of leading capitalist nations like America.*

- *Yet from the biological perspective of the metal-earth, and its company-mothers, what this means is to churn a constant stream of top predator weapon machines and hate memes that kill the mind and the body of the rival human species and when there is so many of them, they literally consume mankind in a war 'eco(nomic)system' when all the resources of the planet are used to kill other human beings. And this is the biggest secret of capitalism, which the FMAsters and its placebo academic social sciences and paper hide, but the cycle of wars of all the papers of biological economics and modern history shows. Every human generation there has been an age of global wars caused by company-mothers because it is 'systemic' embedded in the process of evolution of machines and weapons.*

In the graph, classic economics translated biblical go(l)d values into a digital idol-ogy of placebo mathematical equations that keep cheating mankind into dedicating a surrogate life to multiple lethal weapons and hate memes of maximal profits for its company-mothers and stockratic owners, while underproducing WHealth, welfare goods they need to survive as long as they

are profitable, but what truly meant the 3 fundamental equations of modern capitalism, the equation of productivity (extinction of labor), the equation of profits (multiplication of hate memes, weapons and war) and the Grammatical equation of go(l)d money, Man (salary) = Money = Object (Price) that converts man into a part-time slave compared in its efficiency with a machine, and discharged when the evolution of tools improves its performance. Thus the equations of capitalism with its affinity between industrial weapons, hate media and speculative money cre(dit)ate in the Industrial Age a world similar to that of the animetal civilizations, caused by the 'biological affinity' between gold and weapons in the old 800 years cycle. Today company-mothers in seek of profits overproduce weapons and mental machines of maximal price. So when Profits is all what matters, ultimately the most expensive goods to reproduce, weapons, will become the star-product of the system, enacting the cycles of wars and holocausts, as they ultimately are used in war. The equations of profits of the graph are the DIGITAL LANGUAGE of METAL-MONEY that cre(dit)ates a NON-future for mankind NOT even those who rule understand 'rationally' as they just care to control humanity with its 're=productive organism' of machines, weapons and profits – the company-mother.

The company-mother is the modern structure that carries the equations of maximal profit through production of weapons, speculative money and information machines, which reproduce it along hate memes, enacting the cycle of Industrial wars that substitutes at a much faster professional, generational rate, the old 800 years cycle of nomadic Siberian and Semite barbarians, reproducing weapons in cold and hot deserts, to storm, ravage, rape, kill and destroy the fertile life and love civilizations – so today Smiths and Schmidts, the 'iron-makers' of those tribes are the commonest surnames... All this 'inconvenient' past form of 'capitalism' and 'nationalism' and 'mechanism', is now standardized in an organization that substituted military warriors, kings & aristocrats, Tax-farmers, usurers and magicians with 'professionals'.

When a new top predator organism is born, it multiplies, diversifies and conquers the world with easy, but nothing in the bio-history of this planet can be compared to the power reached by company-mothers in so short time, by taking control of all its physiological networks, (even if mankind still does not know it is a superorganism made of networks; it really doesn't matter; its control means the control of a society and all its citizens-cells):

- First the company-mother **controlled the re=productive language of mankind, digital money**, by inventing a new species with unlimited rights to reproduction - its paper form, stocks. It would be much latter on than by imitation governments printed money in paper and they never will do it in the same amount that stocks do. So the Company became the 'financial, blood' of society earlier on in Amsterdam, where VOC's shares became the money of Holland, and systems of jacking up its prices through speculation, a method of subvention of its armies, which soon monopolized the mass production of gunboats, easily defeating the Iberian empire and provoking a radiation of artillery weapons, sold upstream the rivers that massacred 1/3rd of the German population (30 years war).

Companies ever since have been ahead in the invention of new modes to reproduce digital numbers of money, which only needed the acceptance by politicians of its 'legal tender value' to give a power over society no other institution ever had. How important is this monopoly can be assessed with a simple example. In the earlier XX c. Duke, a monopolist of the Tobacco trade, a drug that injects addictive, lethal tar and nicotine in the lungs, causing an otherwise inexistent disease, lung cancer, as well as other cardiovascular illnesses, which killed an estimated 55 million people in the XX c. a number similar to that of World War II, after the invention of the cigarette – a portable box of 20 monodoses, marketed globally, using 'damned lies and statistics', as Companies had achieved the unthinkable – the right to lie to people, on the products they sold, through propaganda. For a century they got away with murder 'literally', despite the knowledge after world war II of the sole cause of lung cancer: smoking. How they did it? With 3 rights that companies should not have but had acquired 'buying political laws': The rights to lie acquired through advertising laws in the height of the electromechanical age; the immunity of its owners, stockrats, in front of the law for any kind of criminal charges, acquired in the height of the train cycle, through anonymous societies laws; and *the right to invent tender legal money in stock-markets, so they could bribe politicians and buy its laws to no end. Even today after a century of mass murder, they are allowed legally to inject tar and nicotine on the lungs of people to kill them, because after in 1994, Campbell, one of its monopolist CEOs made the mistake of lifting the confidentiality statement of one of its employees that delivered all the reports on addictive and lethal properties to the American senate, they were forced to settle a financial agreement 4 years latter, under the Clinton administration, paying 200 billion in taxes throughout a period of 20 years.*

But this was a financial agreement equivalent to a 40% of taxation that did not take away from them the license to kill.

Beyond the lethality of the product, similar to that of weapons, what impresses of the Tobacco tale is the 'inanity' of the product, completely irrelevant to society – states and governments could not claim as with weapons, tobacco was needed for the defense of its people; and the lack of social and political power of its stockrats – mostly produced in the South, which had lost relevance in American elites after the Civil War; *so it could have been forbidden in the 40s ASAP after the discovery of its lethality; an the fact the world has willingly sacrificed +50 million human lives and counting, only shows that the 'legal, political, financial, informative' structure of the company-mother has such a stronghold of control over all the networks of the superorganism of history that a single man, Duke and then when its cartel was broken into 7 companies, its CEOs could single handily with the help of the propaganda machine of a NYC public relations company, Hill, define a secret strategy of deception, implement it for 50 years without any opposition, by merely printing stock money, profits on price monopoly and buying political clout.* It shows simply enough the aberration of the institution, the true top predator of the world today.

The control on most of the money reproduced in society would be the key to its global power, which made stockrats, the tiny group of financiers, mostly of the earlier biblical sects of the go(l)d chosen in the west, the new aristocrats of the world with absolute rights to reproduce the language of social power that substituted weapons, industrial money, after the defeat of the European armadas that couldn't invade UK, showing that warriors no longer matter, but weapons production defined war. To that aim companies established their control of the 'St-political networks' of laws inventing a system of placebo rights called:

- Capitalist democracies. Modern democracies were invented by the first company-mother VOC, in Holland, by establishing reduced vote rights for owners of shares of the company, or those who had an amount of taxation in money or rent, while the Company Herren XVII (board) took over the Amsterdam's parliament, tailoring laws that maintained its monopoly in legal tender money, trade and export-import taxation. VOC was the Dutch government for the remainder of the XVII century, as it provided the gunboat weapons needed to defeat the legitimate Habsburg kings; but to oust what at the time seemed the biggest unthinkable anathema of society – to depose a king and criminalize its dynasty, something equivalent to deny God, a propaganda machine, the printed press was greased and mass produced libels against the dynasty. Again here, as in the tobacco tale, it does not matter the fact – an absentee king, foreign troops from its other European possessions, religious wars, etc. but the creation of a system of control of the 3 'essential networks' of a social organisms:

Tt>Ts-military, defensive systems > §T]-Reproductive, financial systems >St-informative legal an verbal mass media systems

Within a decade of its foundation VOC had absolute control of the 3 systems of power of Holland and it will never relinquish it, in any country in which it became established, as it multiplied its numbers, diversified its products, but always kept its near monopoly on the production of weapons, legal tender money and political laws purchased to corrupted lawyers, which systematically in the leading 'capitalist democratic culture' (Anglo-America), were company lawyers (so even the American r=evolution started as a dispute on taxation between British and American companies, which threw the tea cargo of its English rivals, and the first presidents were plantation owners of the cargo sent through those gunboat companies).

The lack of a humanist macro-economic science substituted by the organic evolution of company-mothers.

We can return to the beginning of this introduction to 5D social sciences, to express in more sound foundations the main truism of 4D social ideologies: they are NOT a science, because mankind is controlled by the raw power of animetal institutions, today converted into company-mothers of speculative money, machines and weapons, ran by its 3 equations of capitalism, the equation of profits that maximize the production of 'software hate memes' of minimal cost, weapons of maximal price-sale profits and speculative money based in 'techno-utopian' selling of a rosy future, which SUBVERTS the essence of science – to create predictable accurate models about the future to mold it to the benefit of mankind, the 90%, NOT the 10% of managers and stockrats that run the world, and have established through classic economics, the brain child of employees of financial and industrial corporations of Imperial Britain, our 'worldview' on how the economic world should be ruled, for and by stockrats and company-mothers NOT for the benefit and needs of humanity, and its sustainable planets, Gaia and History, and its civilinations and welfare goods. It is NOT rocket science, but censorship is so perfect and the control of the physiological NETWORKS of mankind so thorough that people have after II world war, with the expansion of propaganda 'Goebbels' methods to industry, even forgotten what means 'social freedom' (control of social languages of power, bills of money through a demand economy based in the issue of money as a Universal salary, to reproduce welfare goods people need to survive), 'political freedom' (control of bills of law, through politicians who are hold accountable as in Greek Democracies to its voters,

after tenure, with judgmental votes; prohibition to other institutions, specially company-mothers, to buy those laws), informative freedom (transparency on information regarding companies work, production and lethality, political handling of laws, and propaganda on products, proper teaching of true science and social evolution, the natural love-goal oriented Universe.

The running of the world by company-mothers of machines and its terraforming to the image and likeness of its offspring through bought laws to placebo democratic politicians, divided in bipartisan systems that cater to war and peaceful lobbies of those corporations run smoothly the HAM (Hebrew>Anglo>American 3 ages go(l)d culture) because there is a complete synergy between religion, political and economic structures since the 'Hebrew bible' in the reformation established the go(l)d values above the wor(l)d values in society. So we follow the industrial and political 72 years generational cycles of war and peaceful machines in the leading Industrial r=evolutionary civilization with mathematical precision. But as the 72 years crash markets of overproduction of the synergic information, speculative and transport-military machines of the Ham culture expand globally to all corporations entangled by global stock-markets, the HAM perfect superfluidity for mechanical evolution suffices for the system of evolution of the metal-earth and extinction of Gaia and Historic civilizations to expand to all other nations, reason why we have been for 30 years predicting the future with the true model of macro-economics, 'bio-economics and bio-history', which is the true science of macroeconomics. What universities teach are 'corporative idol-ogies' and the science of microeconomics, of PRODUCTION. So Corporations do achieve its goals of evolution and re=production of machines with perfect efficiency, evolving as superorganisms. This is what I learned the years I frequented system sciences congresses The only goal of systemics was to evolve as perfect organisms corporations. But the understanding of organic history and the collateral effects of company-mothers on Gaia and the Earth of History were taboo.

So Economics is completely biased in favor of the metal-kind, and there are taboos and censorship of any lethal effects. It is impossible to explain the lethal nature of its 3 equations, the equation of profits that multiplies lethal goods, the equation of productivity: Max. Reproductivity = Max. Machine labor/ minimal human labor, that guides the substitution of human labor by machines and robots and ultimately aims to create self-reproductive company-mothers independent of mankind. Those are the two most important equations of capitalism, and one is ignored and the other is amazingly enough, as it is a crystal clear equation of two terms, rhetorically interpreted to deny that it means the automation of all companies and loss of human labor. And finally the syntax of money as a language which compares humans and machines buying both for a price – the equation of the values of metal that invented slavery as opposed to the grammar of human languages that make man the subject actor of the verb and controller of the object:

Man (subject > Verb (action) > Object (energy of the subject) vs. Man (cost-salary) = Money = Object (price)

Δ Speculative money=Δ Top predator weapons of max. price/sale profits +Δ Media hate memes of min. cost/sale profits

Δ Re=productivity = Δ capital in machines / ∇ Human labor -> Reproductivity = ∞ as Human Labor = 0.

The Capitalist system is based in this 3 set of equations, the first on the different grammar and values of money and words, the second on the tendency towards the obsolescence of humans in labor and war fields and the 3rd in the lethal goods reproduced without limit to maximize profit according to the values of the first equation, which in turn determine the second and 3rd equations (as human labor has no value in metal-money, and weapons have maximal value). So the 3 equations are entangled and closely related to the biological laws of affinity established by the earlier Ham (Hebrew>Am Segullah) culture. The second

3 EQUATIONS OF CAPITALISM & GO(L)D CULT(URE)S: 'NERVUS BELLI, PECUNIA INFINITA: I: Max. Profits (inflationary money) = Max. Price-Sales (weapons) + Min. Cost: Informative Hate Memes

The 3 ages of metal-communicators

Go(l)d cult(ure)s & its modern idol-ogy, Creationist Economics (capitalism) has 1 mandate, go(l)d profits maximized by weapons & hate-memes So they overproduce Segregational Memes against Mankind(racist history books: Bible, Mein Kampf; victimism: Holocaust Industry; hate media) 2) evolution & overproduction of weapons (800-80 y. cycles of wars & holocausts),& inflationary money (taxation,usury debt, speculative money) .

III:Max. Profits=Re-Productivity = Max. Machine Labor (capital)->∞/Min.Human Labor->0 =Goal: Automated Company-mothers

Universal Ecosystem	Economic-Antiethic Ecosystems: metal	Historic -Ethic ecosystems							
+ survival	Expensive: gold & Weapon&Machine	Good: social love							
- extinction	Cheap: life, Nature	Evil: war, go(l)d And weapons.							
Language of Existence	Money	Wort(Jds)							

II:Man (min.value)=Money=Object (slave) 'Stock-rats' issue money in corporations with absolute rights to profits.Labor is expendable.

equation can be considered then the equation that ran the British Empire and expanded its military power and hate memes against all other cultures. While the 3rd equation of self-reproductivity and automation runs today the American empire. So we see as in many other entangled systems between language, space, time and scale, how the 3 equations of the HAM culture in its 3 ages have determined and designed the future of this civilization and as it expanded globally the future of all cultures of mankind. We repeat 5D social sciences is not rocket science, it is crystal clear, it is a scientific model that defines the future with its linguistic equations of metal-money and companies production, the only problem is that those goals are not human, both in praxis and idol-ogy in favor of a world in which company-mothers of machines and weapons, the 'free citizens' of the market have complete rights to reproduce any goods and sell them for a profit, because this is considered 'progress', while human goals and lives are expendable.

The 2 paths of the future: Rational social sciences. How to control the evolution of Earth and its 3 biological ages.

The evolution and reproduction of speculative money, lethal machines and weapons (profit equation of capitalism) based in the anti-live values of 'metal-money', opposite to the humanist values of verbal thought (syntax equation of the HAM culture and the word), which make humans expendable and obsolete in labor and war fields (equation of self-reproductivity), *form a ternary structure in time and space that defines the superorganisms of capitalist democracies and design its future, terraforming Earth to the image and likeness of its machines, due to the control of all the physiological networks of society since the creation of top predator company-mothers that invented in Holland the modern world:*

- Tt-companies of weapons>Ts-transport companies>SJJ-financial companies>St-media companies>Ss-mechanist science

The previous equations require the understanding of complex cyclical time and 5D laws, which we will consider next, because mankind along the evolution of those corporations and machines have simplified its view of the organic Universe forgetting the 'verbal causality' that determines the cycles of life and death of systems, as time became reduced to sequential digital numbers in a mechanical clock. So before we return to social sciences we will introduce the laws of the organic Universe. We wanted though first to explain why in a capitalist culture history has no future – because history is NOT the history of company-mothers and its offspring of machines, weapons and speculative money for the 1% but of the human mothers, for whom there is no credit to create a human reality. And yet the SS-elites do NOT care as long as profits keep coming to their reduced 1% in a suicidal collective act that again brings the conclusion that 'barbarians are slaves, because they believe they don't reason'. (Aristotle on those SS-cultures).

How this new brave world invents the future? Only with money, created today mostly in stock companies. But for that future to be desirable it must be a fairy tale as it was the gold religion, when the believer paid gold coins to the banker-priest was told to reach immortality and happiness in the future. Today we are told every new machine is progress and will improve our future. All has changed to remain the same. Still when we study in depth the two sides of the graph, we realize the people on the bottom, prophets of life and love are the responsible for the creation of the collective subconscious minds of the 7 civilizations of mankind we shall study in those papers of History in Space, and they can easily be classified according to their leaning towards religions of life and love (Africa, Islam, Latin America) religions of the machine (Europe, Anglo-America), or are swimming between both waters (Indonesia & Asia); and we will analyze in depth their origins and beliefs. The two extremes of the graph however are self-evident. Africa is the culture of life. Unfortunately Anglo-America, the culture ruled since its modern foundation by company-mothers of machines and weapons and its idol-ogies that worship metal above man, the most perfect organism of Nature as the measure of all things (nationalism, capitalism and mechanism) have won the battle of history. So today the Siberian warrior and Semite Go(I)d cult(ure)s (Ab. SS-culture) that originated them are the 'global culture' that spread its memes and idol-ogies to the entire world, to the rhythm of its company-mothers, which keep evolving and re=producing those machines and weapons, under the pretension of an economic science, *invented by workers of company-mothers or bankers of the biblical culture in imperial Britain, which focuses only in the reproduction and evolution of machines.* In the graph, a fast review of that Industrial r=evolution and its generations: the Industrial R=evolution is the Evolution of 'Mememes of metal', Machines & weapons, systems made of hard metal (iron) and Money, a digital language made of informative metal (gold, also used in the chip connections of computer cycles, now converted into e-money). So we can divide its evolution in the same phases that evolve any organism, and consider in history the nation that evolves them to be in each phase of the Industrial revolution the top nation of the world as it will use its 'evil=anti-live' twins, weapons, to conquer the world.

Tea Party to protest a tax on tea.

1688:
Louis XIV
invades
Holland.
Dutch King,
army,
money & institutions - Bank, Stock-market,
Merchant's parliament - move to England.

In the graph, placebo democracies were founded by gunboat companies in 3 daughter cultures, 1st in Holland then in England and finally in US, controlled ever since by the corporations of max. profit of each Industrial cycle

How FMAsters maintain that monopoly on the information of our societies and hide it to mankind? The key is complexity. Systems in nature grow in complexity from a 'clear-cut' simple beginnings that all people understand.

When the present dictatorship of corporations started in Amsterdam in the XVII century, it was fully understood: the Herren XVII, the board of the first gunboat and slave corporation (VOC), invented money in stock-paper, gave orders of production of gunboats, and used them for piracy, 3rd world colonization and human cheap slave cargo.

Soon it controlled Holland, its weapons defeated the king, installed the first 'capitalist democracy', governed by VOC, whose members were also elected to the parliament, which had only a 'party' (orange party) and chose laws to cater the needs of war and trade of the 'Company'. Stocks then invented money bubbles, whose only purpose was NOT to create wealth, but just print digital numbers called 'money', a mere language of information.

So the free invention of money did not mean wealth creation, as any excuse was good to 'print money', even to speculate with worthless 'flowers' that died fast. This is the equivalent today to invent money with worthless Internet companies. The goal is not to create real wealth but to print 'first' money and then use it to control the world with orders given with it.

This, was also obvious when the dictatorship of financiers and corporations moved to England with the Glorious Revolution, when the Dutch king and financiers gave a coup d'état, threw the British legitimate king, paid 2 million guilders to each MP and installed the City. The same process happened there, including bubbles to invent money with any excuse – the most infamous being the South-Seas bubbles, followed by the exportation of the system to France, who duly created the Louisiana Bubble.

In both cases, 2 worthless companies with 'imaginary' wealth in 'imaginary' gold mines in Louisiana and Argentina (never mind the mines did not exist, the lands were not even under control by British and French governments), corrupted the 'kings' (Louis and the 'German' imported 'first' Windsor), giving them massive amounts of free shares in worthless digital money, to have the backing of 'politicos' when the bubble exploded.

In England it meant the printing of massive amounts of free money, and the final control of the private bank of England and the crown by City bankers – which still continues. In France it meant the end of the monarchy and the beginning of the process of poverty and economic crises that lead to the r=evolution.

In all those cases the trick is simple: private dynasties of 'bankers' control the west with their financial-media systems by printing 'digital and verbal information' (the complementary part of the industrial-military systems that reproduce machines and weapons), used to take over the 'right' of societies, to print money, by corrupting the political-military establishment.

This is what they do and have been doing since the system was invented in Mesopotamia 3000 years ago – that old is the whole thing. Once bankers achieve this fact, they control the financial-media system with the informative machines that print money (then newspapers and stock-papers).

So they seek for 'scholars' that invent complicated arguments to justify their monopoly – and this is the origin of Classic Economics, invented by Adam Smith, a client of the Montagu family, founder of the Bank of England (latter bought by the Rothschild syndicate of 'Am Segullah' Bankers); Ricardo, a stock-broker speculator and Marx (from an Am Segullah dynasty, which focused his 'blame' on productive managers, instead of parasitic private banking).

It is at this STage in the XVII – when in the Glorious R=evolution, the capitalist system moved its center to London, protected sea & gunboats – when the system truly acquires global form, thanks to the private bank of England, through a method, which is so profoundly anti-humanist that has been hidden under the ANTI-QUANTUM paradox of social sciences (the scholar services power, does not objectively analyze it, as he is at the mercy of him – a fact which even Britannica acknowledges as a limit to the lack of development of historic sciences).

The Bank realized his monopoly on the issue of paper-money required to produce as much of it, with financial bubbles, that is credit to stock speculator, and war, that is credit to British government, which should wage war to repay the interests of the loans. Thus war became the fundamental way to win money with debt and fueled the British empire, in as much as the number

of 'action orders' provided by paper-money was much larger than those provided by 'gold-metal', which was the currency of the enemy Global Iberian Empire, crafted on a Renaissance, Roman classic frame of mind (Spain & Portugal, which at the time had conquered the 'coastal surface' of the World). War has been endemic in the west ever since; and along it a second kind of 'rhetoric' besides the 'capitalist' one became staple food as the British Imperial Method spread in Europe in the XIX c:

– A fascist (taking here from the Latin word 'fasces' mask) system of nationalistic, mechanist, war memes, which sanctified weapons and machines as source of progress for the empire – the Wealth of nations, which we contrast with real human WHealth proper of a humanist, rational world based in the laws of social love of Darwinism to the members of the same species, scientific justification of Love religions and socialist movements.

This was a clear regression in the evolution of History in human terms, and the beginning of a planet dedicated to the evolution of machines and weapons, as its only goal.

Today corporations and financiers print 90-95% of the money of the planet and governments 5-10%. People on the other hand does not print any money, and the result is obvious: Monetary orders given by corporations (salaries, 'subsidies' to politicians that buy laws in favor of their machines, and work orders to reproduce and evolve those machines, make a world to the image and likeness of those machines, where humans barely survive. The amount of money invented by and for corporations in stocks is so huge that in fact Apple is worth more than the entire population of the 5th largest country of the world.

And this is telling us that humans are worthless for corporations who value more every MacBook air, as the one I am writing now in, that every person of Bengal, a country, which was at the time the first important British corporation, the East Indian company, bought it, the wealthiest per capita land of the planet. Then the company obliged its '30 million units of human capital to produce instead of rice, export crops, to fill up its 'reproduced machine', the gunboat, and so ½ of its people die of hunger in 20 years, making the price of its stock 'skyrocket'.

It was the first of the many 'hidden genocides of company-mothers of machines, which show they are not truly human systems, but systems for whom the only thing that matters is the evolution, reproduction, sale and profits obtained with the manufacturing of its machines.

Politic & economic censorship in the no future of the globalized HAM world.

The structure of reality is complex, but easy to understand if the reader stop 'believing' in the system and reason it. This is what the system by imprinting e-motionally people has successfully avoided, establishing a placebo fiction dream of chaotic biological freedoms while the $\Delta+1$ social structure is completely structured in a hierarchical predatory form. The U\$ which is the top nation of the world pyramid is an example, because it is NOT a nation but the sum of all human cultures, displaced into the technological future, mimicking the 'scalar' structure of the 7 civilizations of mankind. As such it has many levels of reading. The hierarchical structure of power explains the not so obvious fact that 'orders' come from top, through those who issue money in near monopoly, private bankers that also 'double' as public bankers and give its money to corporations and \$elected politicians, with a 'false choice' of bipartisan structures, as politicians are NOT voted a posteriori as in real Greek Democracies and Companies for their performance, punished when they harm people; nor they can emit freely (deficit zero laws) money which they must extort to people. So the rulers of 'capitalist democracies' are financiers; stockrats. But they obey their 3 idol-ogies that took them to power through animetal ab=use of people: capitalism, nationalism and Mechanism/techno-utopia, and they work together with weapons (External military and internal police). Company-mothers that reproduce weapons also control the military, which has become a lobbyist for the industry. So we see how the pyramid evolved from XIX c. with 'individuals' on top and higher military/nationalist 'old 800 years cycle power', into XX c. pyramid with companies on top and financial companies above, to XXI c. with AI algorithms increasingly digitalizing those 3 idol-ogies. On the bottom of the pyramid a fictitious 3rd class (as any organism has only two equal neuronal/informative and body/working classes, and the 3rd preyed class is NOT of the same species), of enemies, unemployed, people sacrificed and substitute by machines and weapons in labor and war fields. This fictitious 3rd class has evolved and grown, from non-technological cultures (colonial racism), to less industrialized nations (world wars, when the world was conquered but weapons' industries kept the 'pecunia infinita belli nervi cycle killing at home' inferior races – Nazism was just colonialism applied to Europeans). The problem is that as AI robots become superior to humans in all labor fields, this 3rd class will encompass all humanity but the stockrats and attached 'neuronal submissive' people-castes of politicians whose role is to 'cheat' people making them think they have control, while selling their laws (as they don't issue

Konrad Lorenz and the ... Baptist church ...

money) to companies with maximal profits. This leads to the extinction of life and mankind in the III millennium, and ultimately also those stockratic parasites on top, as their function is null and AI programs of 'classic economics' that seek for absolute self-reproductivity and maximal profits by production of weapons, machines and speculative money direct the system in an automated way. This is the birth of metal-earth. Who are the people on top then can be seen in terms of the 7 civilinations of mankind according to the absolute time arrow of future in a world ruled by those 3 'religions of metal':

Gaia: Llife Africa>Indonasia>Islam> History:Mankind>Latin-America>Asia>Metal-earth>Europe>Anglo-America>Stocckrats.

That is the real pyramid whereas the 7 civilinations suffer in higher measure the closer they are to the life and Historic earth according to the times in which their prophets of life and love came to enlighten them. Above them all though as the system globalizes there appears a copycat structure similar to that of Anglo-America, with Financial Stockrats on top (which are the original go(l)d culture of the Habiru>Am Segullah, Hebrew people in Anglo-America, parts of Europe and Latin America, but is imitated by local elites that moved from warrior and political classes to financial & industrial elites). All this structure is copied from the inner America=Humanity in small, and so we talk of Humanity (bottom class) > Managers & political/military/liberal workers for...>Stockrats, as the new globalized class. On top of the stocckrats, if we are to analyze each subgroup, the Anglo-American Financial-Media-Academia (FMAsters) overwhelmingly belonging to the original go(l)d culture set the trends everywhere, imitated by repetition (75% of CEOs of Wall street & Evilwood), protected of all criticism by political, economical correctness and the rewriting of History. The system thus have stringent 'ENTROPIC limits' to any true analysis from any level of depth of social sciences. Only here, in Latin Europe where humanism is fading but still respected, we can perhaps talk a bit about reality. This is the trade-mark of extinction, which I call the Neo-Paleolithic: a Species that is 'farmed', as in Orwell's masterpiece, anim(et)al farm, loves the master human and defends its exploitation. This is the pecking order: American elites absorb all the financial resources of the world through Goldman Sachs, and Bloomberg platforms, and displaced into the future have the top internet metal-earth's brain companies so their middle classes have a high standard of life, and 'close their eyes' to the brutal destruction of all other cultures of the '3rd world' with the exception of the few European and Asian nations and local elites that imitated them. Yet in America, the 3rd class of negros and Latinos (those invisibles as 'enemies') suffer save the small elite of 'e-motional psylocephalic negros' (artists, athletes) whose function for the TV-SOMA matters. We could go on and on after 30 years of observing, trying to publish, being denied, filling blogs, and small print books on a process I know by heart in the past, present and no future. We are in the last ST-ages, in the entropic=chaotic, death age of huminds, substituted by metal-minds. It is the millennial generation of 'animal humans', biologically free to have sex, food, selfie trips, disconnected of other humans, attached to virtual screens that generate virtual r=evolutions, etc. Matrix, Truman's Show, Orwell, Wells, all are parables that fit, as you cannot do real social sciences. I even worked in evilwood trying to do such parables but mine were 'too real'. Since the bottom line is the fact that the Hebrew, FMAsters (80% Economic nobel prizes, Financial, Media CEOs and western Central Bankers), have spread for 5000 years with its go(l)d=credit monopoly a Subjetive, Segregational, Mechanic, Military, Monetary cult(ure) that denies the love values of the wor(l)d to human life, it enslaves and kills by anoxia. It is a memplex that worships the antihuman values of gold, devising a *SMELLYing method to dress as religion or science a subjective agenda of Segregational Go(l)d rights above the 99 (1st Horizon: Abrahamic religions where they are the chosen of go(l)d race; 2nd Horizon: Classic Economics, where they are 'experts' who must monopolize private banking & cre(dit)ate a Supply economy of lethal technologies to promote imperial war profits; 3rd Horizon: Digital Companies that monopolize e-money credit & 'rank=censor' information ab=using privacy to sell lives as modern enslaved 'commodities':*

Placebo imprinting at e-motional, earlier age. Memes - the genes of history

Thus we need to explain the humble realization then that mankind is neither free, nor very intelligent, or brave enough to understand reality. How this world of idol-ogies and placebo truths that imprint mankind into beliefs instead of reasons came to be, requires from a scientific perspective to recognize a harsh truth humans can be imprinted by the 'Goebbels' method' - if you repeat a lie many times people will believe it' specially in the age of metal-communicator that repeat lies galore both in space to many people and in time many times, so the system can pass as social sciences the idol-ogies that were in the past far more clear. And this means mankind is imprinted from earlier age by audiovisual screens and has been so in increasing numbers since the reformation converted Western Europeans to the segregational racist go(l)d memes of the Bible, restarting an age of massive slavery and gold profit. IT is worth to remember to which bizarre degree such imprinting happens even in the victims of the slave trade.

Because all civilisations are still human, despite its increasing rule by company-mothers of machines and weapons whose biological mandate is to re=produce, evolve and terraform the Earth to the image and likeness of its machines, the key for mankind to walk steadily like imprinted goslings enslaving for an alien species is the placebo, emotional imprinting since earlier age of humans with 'beliefs', ego-trips, fictions and paradise myths of a perfect world to which they become so attached that even when they recognize its falsehood, they keep its denial attitude and keep following the 'bite'; of 'Financial-Media-Academia masters' (Ab. FMAsters) that keep im-printing, money, idol-ogies and Academic pseudo-social sciences and obviously as the 'neuronal informative people-caste' of the system with all its privileges believe also to be experts of the system. How bizarre that imprinting can be shown with just one case. Modern slavery was born when company-mothers of gunboats, the 'owners of US', to complete the triangular trade needed to bring 'cargo' to America on the Atlantic crossing downloaded and exchanged for tobacco and rum. Yet it needed a legal excuse founded in the Ham Damnation, a biblical racist mandate, according to which the blacks and Arabs that had expelled the Siberian charioteers from Egypt, back to the desert, when Ramses learned to make chariots in Nubia, were eternal slaves, because 'Ham', his forebear had peed in Noah. This revenge against a military defeat became Biblical law uphold in American courts to justify the slavery of the 'negro'. And yet today, millions of black people worship Yahweh and his book of history, an obvious gore account of a primitive genocidal, racist people of the Bronze age, who considered themselves the superior race and affirmed a millenarian prophecy, center of its religion (Britannica article on millenarianism: 'at the end of times all the tribes of the Earth will become slaves of Yahweh or become exterminated). The Semite and parallel Siberian, Aryan racist culture of Hinduism that established a system of castes with the farmers of Indian on the bottom as 'dalits' – dark people, who were 'inferior to cows, because cows give us milk, they give us only wheat', have triumphed by degrading the wor(l)d and worshipping the power of go(l)d and money. And so today we have military defending tribal nations and a globalized system of parasitic money, ruling over the world. While the humanist, legalist, rational, scientific Greek-Latin-European-EU alternative path to a united World based in diplomacy, welfare and life and love goods, withers away. Among the SS sub-cultures, the most successful has been Judaism, because of its long belief in the values of go(l)d, which acts today as the 'informative head', in control of the Informative machines of Anglo-America (Wall Street, Hollywood), itself the leading civilisation of the world as it started and has always lead the industrial r=evolution of machines. Together they form the Financial-Media (head) Military-industrial (Body) economic ecosystem of company mothers of machines, which rules the world. But of course all this is hidden by the soma culture of fiction placebo freedoms called 'capitalist democracies'. Judaism has also imposed a control of information on its leading role in the role of the SS culture, through camouflage and victimism, by rewriting history and providing an unending flow of fiction thought, happy dreams, selfies and religious somas, as old as its biblical texts. Soma was the hallucinogen substance the Siberian charioteers, who called themselves 'destroyers of cities', 'killers of the dark people', drunk in the altar of Indra, God of war, expert in rape, murder, a charioteer and player of 'dices' (Rig Veda). S.O.M.A. is not surprisingly the name given by the FED to its complicated model of invention of money for 'banker-priests', experts in killing by anoxia, mankind with no credit, as people should have in a healthy supœrganism of history the right to a universal salary in oxygen to create a demand-based welfare economy instead of an offer, animetal, weapons of maximal prize and hate memes based economy from the top to the bottom based in the equation of profits.

So as systems become more complex, the animetal cultures of the past which still dominate our elites become 'scientific classic economics' with equations of profits that do the same, their religions of hate memes did in the past: to multiply weapons of mass destruction and hate memes against the 90% of mankind, while keeping for a tiny elite all the profits of the system, based in a constant evolution of machines and weapons. And even those primitive religions are conserved. Today Hinduism is the religion of the 'dark people' and the Bible and its chosen race is worshipped in USA, whose modern Siberian charioteers, the military, and Semite gold priests, the 'Financial-Media-Academia Masters', rule with iron fist in velvet glove their 'flock', printing money for themselves and their company-mothers of machines and weapons, which produce ½ of the world weapons to kill in unending wars the same Arabs as mercenary soldiers for apartheid Israel and the same negros with police squads that the Ham damnation condemned to eternity. The Ham Culture (Habiru traders>Am Segullah banker-priests) ARE experts in **HAtE Memes**, natural to their earlier trade in weapons (expensive, profitable sale), slaves (cheap human labor) and information easy to spread, today by Hertzian free waves to promote the 'Pecunia infinita bellum nervi' cycle of war that promote profitable trades based in the values of metal. *It is the equation of capitalism, which still holds in the world of company-mothers, reason why capitalist cultures have produced war systematically, to maximize the production of 3 goods: Speculative Money, weapons & information.*

The reason is obvious, profits IS money, and speculative money multiplies ad maximal the fetish digital numbers by projecting mathematically ALL the benefits of the future into the present. This process of 'time reversal' became far more profitable than tax-farming and usury interest, in which people were exploited' out of nothing (for not just, ethical reason), by the coalition of warrior kings and tax-farmers of the SS dual culture, year after year, as we explain in the papers on the Anglo-American culture (the quintessential SS culture, where it is more proper to do a detailed analysis of its 3 horizons, Siberian-Semite Age, British Empire and American digital era). Stil, despite the injustice of tax-farming and usury, imposed by military power twice (the peasant had to pay a tax in species to the warrior king, but then the Am Segullah convinced the Siberian kings to make the tax payable only in go(l)d so the peasant had to borrow gold from the Ham culture and pay an interest that run usually at 50% annual, provoking when defaulting for bad weather the sale of its children as slaves, often castrated in the Middle Ages for the eunuch trade, source of much hate and pogroms).

The SS 'aninetal' culture *eliminated from its memetic structure any social love, the + arrow of time future in the organic Universe, according to the duality of ethics equal forms love and evolve together but different species hate and ab=use each other and metal IS a different atom. So if you worship metal and murder or parasite people with weapons & go(l)d you can't love but segregate from mankind –so gold & iron imposed racism & HAtE Memes. But the wor(l)d carries naturally the values of love and life, so a world of myths, fictions and anti-live=evil values from Loki, to the war gods to the segregational racist hate memes of the Ham culture developed and still continues now spread by the Goebbels' method of repetition. So metal biased love and life cultures and its social truths into segregational, hate idol-ogies.*

The hierarchical class structure of capitalist democracies.

'Presidents are \$elected not elected' Roosevelt. In the graph, humans do not need to understand the laws of economic systems and evolution. As long as they follow the capitalist belief that money justifies it all, as money has maximal price in weapons, they will overproduce weapons and cause wars. As long as they worship machines, they will keep evolving them living a surrogate life of progress. As long as their technoutopian and tribal religious and nationalist idol-ogies, divide humans by race and culture, they will despise men with primitive technologies and kill them. So our civilization ruled by the Informative machines the Financial-media head and the energetic Military-industrial body of company-mothers becomes an automaton of reproduction and evolution of machines, guided by the equation of profits of the FMMI system of stocks and its flows of e-money seeking maximal profits, which is responsible of the 72 years generational≈national cycle of capitalism that switches synergies between inflationary money and consumption goods v. hate media and weapons consuming humans with mathematical precision every human generation, when overproduction of inflationary money and machines cannot be sold as new mechanisms substitute labor. So capitalism switches to weapons and hate media, pays war-monger politicians that consume arsenals and people. So the XXI c. graph which was done 25 years ago in an exhibit of conceptual art at NY reads today (5D social sciences as all sciences do predict accurately the future): the reproductive middle class must be lowered down to the lower scale, maintained cheaply, watched with robot police, and the pandemic scare is helping a process I Thought it would be implemented through war. It has been implemented through pandemics. But it is NOT conscious. Here is where radical humanism fails to understand the pyramid. Not even the Hebrew FMAsters understand it. It is the organic systemic laws of creation of a new species NOT individual groups that are 'local' in its spacetime span. I.e. the FMAsters are also experiencing a 'regression' of its mental IQless mind (inglish word composed of I=ego, IQ and clueless). So they return to the Bronze age civilinations of go(l)d worship and blatant segregation from the slave people they priced (apartheid Israel ½ orthodox population); they just standardize their behavior trying to absorb as much go(l)d as possible, without looking beyond (the old Apuleyan golden a\$\$ metaphor, with blinders, seeing nothing of the suffering of mankind) and just use all possible preventive measures as they expect the exploitation of mankind to explode in wars, r=evolutions and holocausts (victimism, rewriting of history, preventive wars, police states, control of bipartisan politicos, political and economic censorship=correctness, massive fiction mind erasing). Is this then a perception of the future? No. Because all those elites in all those nations believe in the original idol-ogies. So what does create really the future? The top of the pyramid, a series of mathematical cycles of topological evolution of machines which I already predicted in 1992 forecasting the crash of e-money in 2001 and 2008, 72 years after the 1929-1937 crashes that lead to II world war. This evolution of machines in 3 ages of discovery, reproduction of consumption goods, crash of overproduction switch to war machines and information machines in parallel synergy producing first speculative money and then hate memes, has repeated in all cycles and it is going to repeat in the robotic cycle. You cold make a killing in the market knowing that. And in the

3 EQUATIONS OF CAPITALISM & GO(L)D CULT(URE)S: 'NERVUS BELLI, PECUNIA INFINITA:
I: Max. Profits (inflationary money) = Max. Price-Sales (weapons) + Min. Cost: Informative Hate Memes

FMMI 3 CYCLES OF OVERREPRODUCTION OF MACHINES, STOCK CRASHES, SWITCH TO WEAPONS & WORLD WARS THAT CONSUME MANKIND IN CAPITALIST DEMOCRACIE:
1830-1857: Train age | 1857 crash | 1860s war | 1870-1920:oil engines. | 1929 crash->tank wars | 1950-2000:metalminds gadgets | 2001-8 crash:robot wa

<p>I phase. Overproduction of Money & Machines:</p> <p>II Phase: Overproduction of Weapons and Hate-Media</p> <p>Working Machines & Weapons Informative Machines & Money</p>	<p>I phase. Overproduction of Digital Money & Machines:</p> <p>II Phase: Overproduction of Weapons and Hate-Media</p> <p>Working Machines & Weapons Informative Machines & Money</p>	<p>I phase. Overproduction of Digital Money & Machines:</p> <p>II Phase: Overproduction of Weapons and Hate-Media</p> <p>Working Machines & Weapons Informative Machines & Money</p>
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XIX c. Go (l) d cult(ure)s & aristocracies on top XX-XXI: Class system: FMMI company-mothers on top

90s I work for a while at Nasdaq, invested in Amazon at 1\$ told my family to get billionaire but had within 2 years so much angst, and guilt that sold it all and became an activist. And lead a misery life because the bottom line of mankind is that you need in an organism a critical mass of intelligent, ethic people to change that pyramid. And there is no enough. I wasted my life, and all what I want know as old Orwell, old Marx, old Trotsky, all those true ethic, intelligent humanists that tried activism (mine failed systematically, only the one against the Nuclear industry had some exposure) without playing with evil, did. If I could advice a r=evolutionary in other planet, I would tell him no to be so pure. I.e. I should have become a billionaire in Nasdaq first and then buy the American presidency next, and only from power turning upside down the system and r=evolve it. This is what is leading me to suicidal thoughts for years, with 2 attempts in the last decade. I failed mankind for hating evil too much. In the Universe to succeed you MUST camouflage. This the Hebrew knew and that is why they won over the Germans obvious evil. The FMAsters camouflaged as victims and so they rule as top predators. A humanist leader had to do the same. So back to the graph as Bio-history failed and I will exit mundi soon, good luck with the last robotic cycle. Each of those cycles start with an energy-bomb age of war, which was the Drone age of Islamic bombing for Apartheid Israel, then comes a peaceful consumption age, which now starts with massive AI investment while mankind suffers anoxia, but has been reduced by pandemic scare and placebo global warming activism (paid by solar and nuclear industries to ultimately create self-driving cars with solar skins independent of man). So this cycle of peaceful AI robots and millennial, neo-Paleolithic erased visual violent, selfie, unconnected from other human brains will last till the 2070s crash in a world completely dominated by AI robocars, AI software, automated 3D printing companies trillionaire stockrats, a mass of humans connected to 3D virreal helmets living fictional actorial adventures (all foreseen in the 92 dystopian book). Then after those crashes the long awaited China+Russia vs. India+US III industrial world war with AI Terminators armies re=produced automated ant-hill 3D printing factories in the Himalayan and Yakutian harsh war fields with 'survival instincts' will come together as a species, realizing to maximize their survival they should just kill the weaker

human link and keep working. I'll be dead, thanks God. I didn't deserve to live this long. Jesus was lucky to be crucified earlier. I feel closer to Trotsky that failed to take on Stalin and had to see 10 million r=evolutionaries dead. I failed to take on Wall Street and lived to see this... Last, we said that genes do NOT matter to History as memes code cultures that control the physiological informative networks that imprint people, defining the type of world they build – either a world of Gaia, or a world of History, or the metal-earth. We need now to be more scientific and specific from the higher perspective of 5D as we are diving into the most e-motional element for those members of culture that are not objective, scientific about memes but feel them as their 'beliefs' and identities – or else they would not imprint them to act-reaction as automatons of the process of creation of those superorganisms of History. So we are going to map out the 7 largest 'cultural geographic units of Earth', according to the type of sueproorganism their memes try to construct at global level, Gaia>History>Metal-earth. As we are entangled to this planet, and cultures are supported by its geography and build its networks over them. It is then easy to follow through history, the 800-80 years cycles of evolution of the planet studied above, and a simple analysis of the memes of those cultures, the position of its people in the hierarchies of its networks, company-mothers and nations, with 'accurate' data (difficult to find for the people-castes on top of those pyramids due to organic censorship, but available specially here in Latin Europe where historic truths are highly respected. We shall then focus in a case example, the most relevant as it is the most powerful culture of Metal-earth and its company-mothers, hence the one which creates with credit (cre-dit-ates) the future of this planet and its people in higher measure through its control of information machines that print e-money, audiovisual information spreading its memes and subjective view of History and its goals according to those memes.

Darwin explained the 3 traits of the domestication syndrome: neoteny=infantilism, loss of Intelligence & survival instincts (docility). *Those are the 3 traits of mankind in the age of Metal-minds so we have to accept humans have become domesticated by company-mothers & its machines & weapons, to become its workers=reproducers and vitalizers= consumers the only 2 jobs humans had in the eco(nomic)system, now made obsolete by AI robots that consume and reproduce other machines. So as all 'domesticated' species, animetals will be disposed off in Orwellian fashion without resistance in new wars, Holocausts or by GNA lethal technologies (Genetic editing of virons and virions, Nuclear cosmic bombs- strangelets, black holes or AI machines. But children do NOT understand death. So they reject the truths of 5D social sciences and its r=evolutionary, survival solutions, since only huminds intelligent and brave enough with Max. $\Delta+i$: social evolution & information could control and made History immortal. The future of capitalism is then evident but the distortion mankind has experienced even in its understanding of time and space, and how the future is invented by languages, due to those machines and weapons runs so deep that humans unfortunately today do NOT understand time. So we need to introduce now the most insidious of all the distortions caused by metal in the human sub conscious collective, not those of go(l)d neither those of weapons but those of machines and their reduction of the causality of time to a mere sequence of digital numbers... in a clock.*

Humans should build a global supœrganism where the human re=productive unit, the family, must be served as a free citizen, by the 3 life-enhancing physiological networks of ideal history. Instead 3 ideologies and its people-castes of military & corrupted politicos, private bankers & CEOs protected by anonymous societies & technocrats, engineers & physicists causes the extinction of Gaia and History substituted by Metalearth, a new supœrganism whose 'free market citizens', company-mothers terraform the planet to the likeness of its offspring of machines and weapons - metalife, joined by metal-networks of information (mass-media, internet), metal-networks of energy (electricity, roads, pipes) and re=productive networks of machines (factories), automated as robots and software suites substitute and make obsolete humans in labor and war fields under the law of self-reproductivity=Max. Capital / Min. Human labor $\rightarrow \infty$, which guides all companies and will soon make machines with solar skins and telepathic AI independent of man. This process -> initiated by the Industrial r=evolution is guided by the equation of capitalist profits that builds those 3 networks: Max profits (stock money) = Max. reproduction of goods of maximal price (top predator weapons) & minimal cost (information software reproduced for free by ¥-waves), which happens to be the goods that kill our bodies and minds, and parasitize 'human currency money' that looses value as e-money multiplies the wealth of company-mothers and its 0.01% of owners, stockrats, the new aristocrats of XXI c. societies that issue in monopoly the language of e-money and have no legal responsibility. So *stockrats, robotized companies, internet network and the metal-earth stock-brain of e-money abandons the human economy of the 99%, as we saw in the pandemic, reproducing money only for stockrats and its corporations, as robots consume its machines, leaving History and humans as History did with Gaia and its life species out of the eco(nomic)system, moving ahead the equation of the 3 ages of Earth: **Past (gaia) < Present (history) > Future (Metal-earth)***

PARASITIC CAPITALIST DEMOCRACIES VS. W-HEALTHY NATURE'S SUPERORGANISMS

IN SYSTEMS SCIENCES DIFFERENT ORGANIC SCALES OF SIZE FOLLOW THE SAME LAWS: SOCIAL ORGANISMS ARE RULED BY MEMES HOMOLOGOUS TO LIVING ORGANISMS RULE BY GENES. BOTH HAVE SIMILAR LIFE-DEATH PROCESSES, SICKNESSES & VITAL NEEDS

HUMAN SOCIAL SUPERORGANISMS SUFFER APARASITIC, CANCER: BANKS & COMPANY-MOTHERS OF MACHINES ISSUE 99% OF MONEY: COMPANIES PRINT STOCK-PAPER FOR FREE: 62. TRILLION BANKS ISSUE MONEY IN DERIVATIVES & LOANS: 2 TRILLIONS GOVERNMENTS ONLY ISSUE 67 BILLIONS. **HUMANS NONE.** SO HUMANS WITHOUT CREDIT SUFFER SYSTEMIC POVERTY & LACK WELFARE, EDUCATION, BEING DISPLACED FROM LABOR & WAR FIELDS BY EVOLVING OVERPRODUCED MACHINES, WHICH TERRAFORM THE WORLD TO ITS IMAGE AND LIKENESS

IN A HEALTHY SUPERORGANISM ALL CELLS RECEIVE ITS BLOOD-MONEY DISTRIBUTED TO KICK PRODUCTION OF HEALTHY GOODS. EVEN THOSE WHO DON'T WORK (FAT CELLS) LIVE ONLY VIRAL SICK BODIES USE ALL ITS ENERGY TO REPRODUCE OTHER SPECIES, AS CAPITALISM DOES.

FINANCIAL MEDIA MILITARY INDUSTRIAL ECO (NOMIC) SYSTEM

Virtual Mind anesthesia prevents Mankind to SEE its exploitation by FMMI eco(nomic)system

- Blood needs to go to all living cells including muscles, organs and bones.
- This is so living cells get essential oxygen and nutrients

2008: +1 trillion in taxes sucked in from people's hard work money to buy e-money derivatives

BONES REPRODUCE RED CELLS TO GET OXYGEN -MONEY TO ALL CITIZENS IN A UNIVERSAL SALARY THAT KICKS RE=PRODUCTION & DEMAND OF WELFARE GOODS. AND RE=PRODUCE WHITE CELLS TO KILL ALL LETHAL GOODS, WHOSE PRODUCTION IS REPRESSED

Who Could Issue Money?	What Kind of Money?
Central Bank	Fiat Money A government's legitimacy gives this its value
Commercial Banks	Bank Money Created under central bank supervision
Companies	Private Money : Stocks, Bonds, e-derivatives Can be redeemed against future products or services
Communities	Human beings NO Rights to issue money (Universal Salary). Must pay instead Taxes to get welfare but corrupted governments also use taxes to pay weapons & political bribes.

The last leader of tv-hate ...

Parasites inject anesthetics to inhibit defense systems as Financial-Media System of informative machines do with fiction & hate media to inhibit defense against the financial & corporative monopoly in the issue of money that chokes mankind off credit

MEDIA ANESTHETIC CIRCUS: BIPARTISAN POLITICOS+NAZIONANIST RED FLAGS+WARS+VIRTUAL REALITY HEROES+SELFIES

Unfixable' boot ROM security flaw in ...

Chemists Design New Compounds That ...

Massive Black Hole Mystery Solved Wit...

EPILOGUE: GNA RISKS.

According to 5D metrics, $\$ \times T = C$; the smallest species in space, reproduce faster in time and win in the struggle

for existence. The biggest existential dangers for mankind do not come from larger forms, national struggles or the global warming of Earth but from efficient species co-existing with us in lower planes of space-time, whose 'reproductive and evolutionary radiations' fast outpace human capacity to contain them.

In the graph the 3 top predator species of the economic ecosystem (chips, robots, AI), the biological ecosystem (coronavirus) and its nano-technologic replicas (metal-viruses, 'virons') and the matter, galactic ecosystem (black hole, strangelets), which have become with the advance of technology (electronic industry, Crsprs-9 genetic editing, high energy accelerators) the 3 key existential dangers for humanity in the XXI c.

As an activist who has tried for decades to denounce those existential risks with little results due to the egocy (Ego=idiocy) of mankind, the coronavirus crisis did not surprise me. It was expected and yet it is of the risks poised by lower $i-1$ planes of existience, the less dangerous for humanity.

The top predator species of matter, a baby black hole or heavy quark strangelet, if reproduced by the industry of accelerators would take a few hours to destroy Earth, feeding at light speed in the matter of this planet. The chip radiation and all its applications are making obsolete humans in labor and war fields. And its application to the design of nano-bacteria, able to eat metal and reproduce its form would mean the extinction of the planet by a grey-goo in 3 months. Finally the top predator of life, a viral coronavirus, which mixes the killing efficiency of the SARS species and the maximal expansion rate of the Universe (a perfect exponential $e=2.8$ speed of propagation). *The equations of growth of a baby black hole are also simple. Hawking discovered that equation: $\Delta Mass = K/\sqrt{Temperature}$. Fine, as a black hole is born hot, it evaporates according to the 2nd law of thermodynamics the environment and feeds on it. This is what we see on the Universe happening all the time. So if they do it at CERN a baby hole will eat us.*

Chips reproduce much faster than man, there are 100 times more population of metal-minds and at c-speed of thought in more efficient digital languages, with a cost close to a few dollars they are displacing mankind in all labor and war fields, in the economic ecosystem.

The present pandemic is caused by a genetically engineered virus with 3 maximal predator qualities: maximal speed of reproduction, close to the number e, due to its air 'bat' transmission, maximal informative genetic charge of any virus due to its 'pangolin' base and maximal infection capacity thanks its invasive spike membrane, copycat of the ACE2 human key. As the graph shows chances those 3 parts came together in chaotic-random Nature's mutations are null. Intelligent design with the new genetic viral editing tools, Crisprs-9 easy. The only 'reason' virologists adduce to deny genetic engineering is that if someone would have engineered it, it would have added a more lethal 'MERS or Ebola' strain. So we are lead to suppose that *virologist not only experiment with genetic tools to create chimeras but they are in fact potential 'genociders'!?* *Fact is Nature cannot do it, humans can do it, and editing virus is much easier than creating supermen, so once the tool was invented they did it. And since they were just 'playing to be God' they did a top virus but NOT the one to wipe out mankind with 40% death rates. Fact is pangolins are protected by scales, so not even ants can bite them and bats NEVER bite pangolins. It is just impossible even a single crossing. But now that the makers of Crisprs-CAS 9 got rewarded a nobel prize, vaccine companies 10-fold price in stocks and a private company is selling in internet the 'do-yourself-kit' with Crisprs-CAS 9, a genocider might get into the business. To make strangelets and black holes is also getting cheaper as Plasma accelerators drastically reduce the size from 100 km. rings to 10 meters – yes you hear well, in a decade a 10 meters 'do-it-yourself' plasma accelerator can create black holes and some idiot in some 3rd rate University might want to*

The miraculous presence of a sick bat flying to infect a sick pangolin where both merged and then mutated this ACE-2 hypercomplex molecule all at once to enter a 'future' Wuhanese that will eat it 3000 miles away; when Nature takes eons to get each atom in its place. Since the virus had to mutate inside the living pangolin probabilities of that chain of miracles a when just 3 cuts & pegs with CAS does the job fast & the technology it and a Nobel ACE-key edited along a bat and Pangolin virus to make COVID

get a Nobel prize proving Mr. Hawking was... deadly wrong. This is then the Age of Entropy of History, when a black swan event propiciated by our idol-ogies and childish attitude=egocy will do us all, as death is a sudden accident that triggers the collapse of a system slowly corrupted to the bone.

So: the exponential growth of smaller 5D systems of a lower plane of existence; and the technological dangers of living in a society whose 'free market citizens', companies, have the right to evolve and reproduce any technology regardless of its lethality for mankind *and sell it in the internet*, will cause our extinction unless those risks are repressed. Since an efficient social organism, as humanity could be if social scientists, 'doctors of history', ruled and designed her according to the laws of organic systems, should not go through those risks for 2 obvious reasons:

- As a single global organism, aware of the 5D laws of existence, humanity would avoid any encounters with those species, meaning the Industry of Accelerators would be banned from testing big-bang production of strangelets and black holes; the Chip industry would be limited to simple models, below the capacity of human beings to control them, and its most lethal species (military and working robots) that make humans obsolete banned. And genetic engineering (Crsprs-9 technology) that makes possible to enhance any lethal virus by editing-into it the most destructive genes of other sub-species, repressed.

Mankind faces those risks iwith 'egocy: ego=idiocy' which is infinite to our species, due to its complete misunderstanding of the biological, organic nature of the Universe and its 'network intelligence'. In brief, it has no intention under a capitalist system of 'lineal time thought', who believes the species is 'entitled' and has a special place in the Universe, and it is the only intelligent form, etc. etc. to forbid any of those technologies. And if something wrong happens it will accuse always Nature.

This was my experience in the activism and suits against CERN for its attempts to make strange matter and black holes on Earth. The whole point is they could not be blamed if the catastrophe happened. Or as the American West pacific Supreme court who closed the suits (CERN alleged as a cold war European institution diplomatic immunity), 'the destruction of Earth won't be attributable to the American Government' – so the existence of a virus with the qualities of SARS and flu will never be attributed to bio-logic research or else we would have to forbid 'genetic editing' with its enormous 'benefits' for the pharma industry. Fact is since Crsprs-9 exists there has been editing of viruses all over the place. Specifically in the late 2010s a team from the Wuhan virology Institute engineered a hybrid virus, combining a bat coronavirus with a SARS virus that had been adapted to grow in mice and mimic human disease. The hybrid virus was able to infect human cells... This we know. What we do not know are biowarfare similar experiments taken place in the leading nations of the field, US, China and Israel. We know also that to make some extra-money Chinese concerns sell to markets for meat, the monkeys and animals used in experiments – even rats that are consumed in that country.

The most insidious reason of our extinction is 'greed'. Stock-markets sell THE FUTURE speculating in the prize of shares of future companies, and so they MUST sell a rosy future to all technologies to invent money for free. We saw it in the 10-folding of prizes of vaccine companies during pandemic, in the fact Tesla that produces 100th the number of cars than Toyota has overcome it in prize. This is money stocks invent, and then pay the same audiovisual informative companies they own to sell and promote. The FMAsters of Financial-Media-Academia informative companies mostly of the 'childish' subjective lineal Hebrew culture of chosen of go(l)d that cannot be criticized (Holocaust industry) as we do –reason why biohistory doesn't get exposure, the truth is hidden by the Goebbels' method of repetition of liess, will not have it other way. Extinction is part of their culture and they have never even recognized the economic, cyclical nature of wars and holocausts. Good luck.

What is clear is that all the catastrophes that will come in the XXI century will be denied by scientists, and the concept that our species who don't even understand the laws of the 5D scalar, organic Universe will achieve the panacea of supreme knowledge through those experiments will continue. The absurd case of the industry of accelerators, a relic of the cold war, whose observation of the by no means non-proved big-bang theory (false in a scalar Universe, as we analyze in our papers on the Universe and entropy), which can be done with telescope investments, in which I had first-hand knowledge testifies this macho-man attitude of 'military nature', or as Eames put it: 'cemeteries are filled with corpses of people who die in wars

NEWSPEAKS OF ECONOMICAL & POLITICAL CORRECTNESS OBEY PROFITS & GOALS OF COMPANY-MOTHERS & STOCKRATS:

Global warming scare fosters clean energy that will automate robocars & terminators
Free of man with telepathic A.I brains& solar skins & 'cleans' Nuclear cheap electricity

The 3 ages of metal-communicators

Religious revivalism
Holocaust Industry &
Islamophobia backs
Splendid Wars for Profits
Hate memes Industry
& Apartheid Israel (the
Nation of most western
Financial Media-Masters)

'the 2 sacred humanist, caring'newspeaks of correctness are in fact hidden agendas of the Financial/Media-Military/Industrial Supørganism

everybody knew they were never going to happen'. Instead we focus in Global warming, NOT a extinction risk but a publicity stunt to get subventions for new technologies, speculate in stocks and clean up the act of the Nuclear industry that 1st paid it.

But human entropy is so advanced that the suicidal, subjective Hebrew culture has no opposition to its predation and murder of Gaia and Mankind. I left U\$ when Bush took power because to organize its people to help mankind survive was a lost cause. But the angst remained. Could have mankind survived this no future if I could have taught them 5D 1st principles? Am I guilty of abandoning the search for 'resonance'? But Americans were so much into entropic, individual mood that nothing could be done. Still I returned a decade latter for my activism against CERN's doomsday machine and found a few American scholars willing to denounce them. So we had some brain storms on how to proceed, and while all agreed that denouncing Hawking's absurd $\nabla\text{mass}=k/\Delta T$ change of the arrow of thermodynamics to make baby black holes evaporate, instead of doing what they do – to feed on mass, was the best strategy AS NONE had thought of it before I did, they wouldn't sign the affidavit but each as 'independent scholar' would pursuit its own path of denounce. America is a nation of slaves of its FMAsters (Financial-Media-Academia Hebrew culture of go(I)d that controls its machines of information) precisely because they are a perfect entropic surface of points disconnected while the Hebrew elite is at least a 'tribe'. Then there was peer pressure so nobody but Walter wanted to sign the suits as lead, so it ended up being 'Sancho et al. vs. CERN, the energy department, etc.' The astounding level of harassment I suffered during the Bush administration is explained somewhere else. I lost academia positions, got my arm broken the day before the suit, etc. etc. No I remain vaporize.

We shall conclude with the obvious repetitive message: The Universe is a living organism. Machines are evolving and if man stops being the top predator mind of the Earth it will be extinguished by the GNA lethal technologies evolved by chips. For 30 years I have explained this obvious law of survival. Genetic, Nuclear & AI lethal technologies must stop and to do so politicians and military must destroy CERN, a dozen nano-factories of chips and forbid genetic editing or else die. Man needs to kill the child before it becomes a tiger-hunter, the chip before it extinguishes mankind. But the placebo Hebrew>Capitalist go(I)d culture of wishful thinking repeating ad nauseam through its FMAsters and its companies of metal-communicators, its suicidal justification of the holocaust of mankind for the profits of a few billionaires makes the reasonable, seem outrageous and the bizarre – a humanity that sacrifices his children to greed, the new normal. act is stience does not change, nor its laws of survival. And no amount of wishful lies will change those laws above man. *There is no new normal but 5000 years of idol-ogic bull\$hit and human sacrifices of our children to the 7th generation in the altar of Baal, based in egocy (Ego=idioy), denial of the Tree of Life, worship of the Tree of Metal, blind by go(I)d greed to its collateral lethal effects, with the image of the old Levant Go(I)ds, Astarte that converted women in whores, tagged with a gold ring, dancing on the skulls of their own children sacrificed to gold statues signifies. This culture, now global is an aberration against Nature and it won't last unless it obeys it simple laws of survival & cuts the Gordian knot of bull\$hit: The G20 political mind of mankind **should blow up 'peacefully'**, GNA factories and then once we are safe, we can talk how to build a future for mankind – the 99%, not a few FMA stockratic parasites. **This must be clear:** Truth cannot be denied So both truths, our extinction and resurrection are organic. One sides with the metal-earth and it seems more likely due to the shortcomings of animetal cultures in Δ -ethics and i-ntelligence, the Δ_j elements of survival of the organic Univese. So we have to switch back and forth between ideal history, loosing the game of Existence to Animetal entropy. What we WON'T DO is on top of our extinction to forgive and forget with placebo victimism and political and economical correctness what the SS-cultures are doing to mankind committing collective S-ucide. Enough is enough.*

RECAP. 5D History is *inscribed in the 5D scales pf the organic Universe, in a jump of 'quality of thought, scientific analysis of the human experience and understanding of the real causes of Historic events' unlike anything that has happened since Darwin influenced Marx and the socialist school, Butler and its description of 'animetals' and evolving machines, Schumpeter, Kondratieff ,Spengler and the biological schools of History, all denied today by the placebo pseudo-Biblical anthropomorphic view and idol-ogies of nationalism (worship of weapons), capitalism (worship of go(I)d) and mechanism, described in the graph in biological terms. lideal history would repress the lethal goods of metal-earth & promote Gaia in a sustainable world, by reforming the system with the 3 positive and negative measures of reform of those 3 physiological networks of mankind to promote the*

welfare goods of Gaia and History and repress the lethal goods of the metal-earth with legal measures, putting back on top of society, the human natural language of the wor(l)d.

The only coincidence between 5D social sciences and Biblical bigotry: *Intelligent design exists and it is a better biological tool to cre(dit)ate a perfect world than leaving to raw brutish, Earth's evolution our future. A human species in control of his Legal, verbal, nervous language above digital, blood money is possible, equivalent to a mammal which represses lethal poisons and feeds all its cells with right information and energy. Capitalism is JUST a primitive 'worm-like' superorganism, whose blood-money system is above an underdeveloped nervous-legal one, so plants poison larvae with chemicals because the worm does NOT repress its greed. This is the fitting comparison in a 5D Universe in which all systems are organisms and laws repeat at scale. There is NO difficulty designing a perfect world with laws if mankind stops being a worm.*

This is NOT a fantasy but the alternative culture of truth, reason, humanism, rationality, human 'artistic and ethic' l-wor(l)d senses, with man and its mind as the most perfect organisms of an organic Universe on top. This is the goal of my original 'Greek-Latin' culture who invented NOT a placebo of human freedoms but Real democracy, real science, real art=human senses without repressing our natural wantings for reproduction (sex NOT a sin but an orgasm), REAL FOOD, our natural energy (NOT repressive dietary laws against tasty seafood and pork), LOVE to the members of your own species to evolve organically into a

stronger whole (not dog-eat-dog selfie fantasies), etc. etc. The last attempt to create such a world with humans in control of its physiological networks, serving mankind was the welfare state of the European Union, before it became corrupted and dominated by the SS culture with the European Central Bank, no longer issue money for pro-welfare policies, and the Unification of the Germany that have put Latin Europe to the service of AI, 5G, company-mothers of machines and repressive measures against true 5D social sciences with political and economical correctness, denying the entry of Russia in Europe to make the European Union a real 'global force' with an alternative model to the SS genocidal and suicidal culture that is racing full speed towards self-extinction.

In the graph, the cover of the seminal book, c.92 that developed the model of 5D History, predicting the future of its two superorganisms, which would diverge after the 2008 crash of overreproduction of metal-minds and its derivatives, e-money and Pcs, entering in the last age of the Industrial R=evolution, the age of Robots. Hence only an organic understanding of mankind and the metal-earth and the scientific evolution of the physiological networks of humanity to serve the goals of our species could avoid our obsolescence and final demise.

BIO-HISTORY
THE TREE OF SCIENCE

Enz-Y-man

THE 3 ECOSYSTEMS OF HISTORY

Past > Future R=evolution: I: Carbo-Earth > II: Enzyman > III: Metal-Earth
 Forces of Communication: I: Wor(l)ds > II: Pricing > III: Digital Information
 Top Predators: Hunter > Farmer > Prophet > Warrior > Trader > Scientist > Company

III HORIZON : BIO-ECONOMICS: RE=PRODUCTIVE COMPANIES

Radiation of Energy Organs: 'Age of Metal-Bodies': 1768-1928
 Radiation of Informative Organs: 'Age of Metal-Minds': 1928, ±2008
 Living Species: 'Age of Animetals' ±2008 >
 Extinct Radiation: Carbolife. New Bio-system: Metalife

Anti-Universe: The Wor(l)d Union

Human Goods > Ethonomics > Mankind